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Table 1: Document Revision History

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASJC	All Science Journal Classifications
APC	Article Processing Charge
ARC	Athena Research Center
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CWTS	Centre for Science and Technology Studies
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EPO	European Patent Office
ELIXIR	European Life-Science Infrastructure for Biological Information
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FCCN	Fundação para a Computação Científica Nacional
FoS	Field of Science
FWCI	Field-Weighted Citation Impact
GDCC	Global Data Citation Corpus
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HAL	Hyper Articles en Ligne
INIST	Institut de l'Information Scientifique et Technique
IGO	Intergovernmental Organization
IP	Internet Protocol
IPC	International Patent Classification
ISP	Internet Service Provider
LLM	Large Language Model
NACE	Nomenclature statistique des Activités économiques dans la Communauté Européenne
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization

OA	Open Access
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OS	Open Science
PATSTAT	EPO Worldwide Patent Statistical Database
PMID	PubMed Identifier
PSM	Propensity Score Matching
RCAAP	Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal
RDF	Resource Description Framework
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SciNoBo	Science No Borders
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UPEC	Université Paris-Est Créteil
UMinho	University of Minho (Portugal)
UN	United Nations
VPN	Virtual Private Network

Executive Summary

This is a **reference report**, meant to support **reusability and sustainability** of PathOS tools and datasets for OS impact evaluation. It complements the Indicator Handbook,¹ deliverable D3.3 (Open Science Impact Indicators for Case Studies, Final Report), the DMP (D3.5), and technical repositories (GitHub/Zenodo).

The report focuses on the **implementation dimension** of Open Science impact evaluation, detailing how indicators were produced from the datasets, how tools were combined across infrastructures, and what technical and methodological challenges emerged. It highlights the adaptations required to ensure data harmonization, cross-platform interoperability, and reproducible computation of OS indicators under diverse conditions.

The document provides:

- Technical specifications of the data sources and analytical tools used for indicator construction
- Descriptions of the processing workflows and integration pipelines
- Reflections on operational issues such as data quality, classification accuracy, and identifier consistency
- Lessons learned to inform future evaluations and methodological refinement.

The six PathOS case studies collectively demonstrate the implementation of Open Science (OS) impact indicators across a range of disciplinary, thematic, and national contexts. Each applied a harmonised analytical framework but adapted its depth and focus according to the specificities of its data environment, stakeholder ecosystem, and infrastructure maturity.

Most case studies operated with standardised datasets and bibliometric integration workflows. The “French Open Access Infrastructure” case study includes extended documentation due to the legal, administrative, and technical complexity of processing national-scale data under GDPR compliance, ensuring methodological transparency and supporting future reuse of this setup as a reference for Open Science monitoring at national and institutional levels.

WHAT IS COVERED IN OTHER DELIVERABLES

DMP (D3.5)	Descriptions of tools and datasets, licensing, FAIRness, open/closed status, links to GitHub/Zenodo
Zenodo	Host for open datasets, full documentation and metadata
GitHub	Tools’ documentation and (links to) code
D3.3	Methodology and implementation narrative per case study: how the indicators were applied, findings, causality, context
Indicator Handbook	Methods to use tools and datasets in order to get the indicators.

¹ <https://handbook.pathos-project.eu/>

1. Introduction

Open Science impact evaluation requires not only theoretical frameworks but also practical tools and validated datasets that can be applied across diverse contexts. While conceptual indicators provide direction, their real-world implementation demands careful consideration of data sources, technical infrastructure, analytical workflows, and methodological trade-offs that emerge when moving from theory to practice.

This deliverable documents the comprehensive suite of tools and datasets developed and deployed across the six PathOS case studies to operationalize OS impact indicators in real-world evaluation contexts. It provides detailed documentation of how indicators were implemented, what worked well, what proved challenging, and how future efforts can build on these experiences.

The documentation serves multiple complementary purposes within the PathOS project ecosystem. It provides the technical foundation that supports D3.3's empirical narratives and implementation results, while operationalizing the theoretical frameworks established in the Indicator Handbook (WP2).

This report focuses specifically on implementation insights: how tools were used in practice, what was learned from their application, what limitations emerged and need addressing in future iterations, and how the documented approaches enable OS impact evaluation in different institutional and policy contexts. In other words, it emphasizes the practical knowledge needed to apply, adapt, and improve them.

2. Cross-Case Overview Table

To support the sustainable reuse and continued development of the PathOS methodology, the project delivered the **PathOS Toolkit** as part of Milestone 17 (MS17) *“Data and tools packaged and published”*. The repository (<https://github.com/PathOS-project/pathos-toolkit>) consolidates code, case-study implementations, pipelines, and documentation used across multiple case studies. Its structure includes a common template for new case studies, shared methodological assets, and guidance on accessing study-specific datasets deposited in Zenodo. By bundling analysis workflows with documentation, the toolkit provides an operational foundation for future applications of PathOS indicators across new contexts.

The following table summarises which indicators, data sources and tools were reused or developed across the PathOS case studies. It also provides links to the corresponding repositories (e.g. Zenodo, GitHub) and references to the PathOS Data Management Plan (DMP), offering a concise overview of how each artefact supported indicator implementation within each case.

Table 2: Cross-case overview of reused and newly developed PathOS tools, data and indicators operationalized in the case studies

NAME	TYPE	REUSED / CREATED	IMPACT OF ARTEFACT REUSE IN COVID-19 PUBLICATIONS	IMPACT OF OPEN ACCESS ROUTES ON TOPIC PERSISTENCE	PORTUGUESE REPOSITORY INFRASTRUCTUR E RCAAP	EFFECTS OF DATA REPOSITORIES ON DATA USAGE	FRENCH OPEN ACCESS INFRASTRUCTUR E	ELIXIR´S BIOINFORMATIC S RESOURCES	DMP CHECKLIST
SciNoBo (Field of Science Classifier) (link)	Tool	Reused	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓ (link)

SciNoBo (Citation Analysis) (link)	Tool	Reused	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓ (link)
SciNoBo (Research Artefact Analysis) (link)	Tool	Reused	✓			✓			✓ (link)
SciNoBo (Citance Analysis) (link)	Tool	Reused	✓						✓ (link)
SciNoBo (SDG Classification) (link)	Tool	Reused		✓					✓ (link)
SciNoBo (Science-Industry Collaboration) (link)	Tool	Created	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓ (link)
SciNoBo (Clinical Trials/Guidelines)	Tool	Created	✓						✓ (link)

Uptake) (link)									
SciNoBo (Thematic Persistence) (link)	Tool	Created		✓					✓ (link)
OpenAIRE Graph API (link)	Tool	Reused	✓	✓	✓				✓ (link)
Gender Classification (link)	Tool	Reused		✓					✓ (link)
Datstet (data mention extraction) (link)	Tool	Reused				✓			✓ (link)
Automated NACE Domain Classifier (link) (project link)	Tool	Created					✓		✓ (link)

French Open Science Log Explorer (platform link) (link)	Tool	Created					✓		✓ (link)
ElasticSearch (link) and Kibana (link)	Tool	Reused					✓		✓ (link)
IPinfo's Academic Research Program (link)	Tool	Reused					✓		✓ (link)
Lens.org (link)	Tool	Reused						✓	✓ (link)
PATSTAT (link)	Dataset	Reused (processed version from OPIX PC)	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓ (link)
EuroPMC (link)	Dataset	Reused						✓	✓ (link)
CORD-19 (link)	Dataset	Reused	✓						✓ (link)

OpenAIRE Graph (link)	Dataset	Reused	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓ (link)
Semantic Scholar (link)	Dataset	Reused	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓ (link)
ROR.org (link)	Dataset	Reused	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓ (link)
PubMed Data (link)	Dataset	Reused	✓						✓ (link)
Collection of covid-19 related publications (link)	Dataset	Created	✓						✓ (link)
Collection of AI and Climate related publications (link)	Dataset	Created		✓					✓ (link)
Dataset of Portuguese publications	Dataset	Created			✓				✓ (link)

2015-2024 (link)									
Global Data Citation Corpus (link)	Dataset	Reused				✓			✓ (link)
OpenAlex (link)	Dataset	Reused				✓	✓		✓ (link)
DataCite (link)	Dataset	Reused				✓			✓ (link)
Manual extraction of data mentions from 200 SSH publications (link)	Dataset	Created				✓			✓ (link)
Eurostat NACE Rev. 2.1 (link)	Dataset	Reused					✓		✓ (link)
OpenEditions log files	Dataset	Reused					✓		✓ (link)

(link) (restricted access)									
HAL log files (link) (restricted access)	Dataset	Reused					✓		✓ (link)
Final augmented and aggregated log dataset (DMP link) (HAL access advantage link)	Dataset	Created					✓		✓ (link)
Lists of article DOIs (extracted from EuroPMC) (link)	Dataset	Reused						✓ (link)	✓ (link)
List of patent IDs (extracted from	Dataset	Reused						✓ (link)	✓ (link)

Lens.org) (link)									
Citation Impact (link)	Indicator	-	✓	✓	✓			✓	-
Science-Industry Collaboration (link)	Indicator	-	✓	✓	✓			✓	-
Uptake in medical practice (link)	Indicator	-	✓				✓	✓	-
Reuse of code/data in research (link)	Indicator	-	✓						-
Thematic Persistence (link)	Indicator	-		✓					-
Cost Savings (link)	Indicator	-			✓				-
Use of data in research (link)	Indicator	-				✓			-
Availability of data	Indicator	-				✓			-

repositories (link)									
Availability of preprint repositories (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
Availability of publication repositories (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
Prevalence of Open Access publishing (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
Uptake and impact on societal issues (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
Uptake by media (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
Scientific literacy (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
Uptake by policy	Indicator	-					✓		-

makers (link)									
Uptake by patient groups (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
Uptake in education (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
Uptake in the legal sector (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
OS access advantage (link)	Indicator	-					✓		-
Extra-academic collaborations (link)	Indicator	-						✓	-
Innovation output (link)	Indicator	-						✓	-
Diversity (link)	Indicator	-		✓					

3. Case Studies

3.1. Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence

3.1.1. Purpose and Focus (brief)

This case study evaluates whether different Open Access (OA) routes influence the **long-term vitality** of research themes, here defined as **topic persistence**, i.e. the ability of a topic to remain active and influential in the literature over time, in the rapidly evolving domain of **Artificial Intelligence for Climate**. Rather than focusing solely on short-term citation metrics, this study introduces **topic persistence** as a central indicator of Open Science (OS) impact, defined as the ability of research topics to remain active and influential in the literature over time.

The case tests two distinct OS practices:

- **Green OA:** repository-based self-archiving of full texts
- **Published OA:** journal-mediated open publication with a formal licence (Gold and Diamond journals, and Hybrid OA). Bronze and dual-mode OA were excluded to preserve clean treatment definitions

Using a **propensity-score matching** design, a statistical method that pairs **OA articles** with **Closed Access** counterparts that are similar in observable characteristics, it asks whether these practices causally affect not just citations, but also:

- **Topic persistence scores** (a novel indicator based on longitudinal topic activity²)
- **Field-weighted citation impact (FWCI)**, a normalized citation metric that accounts for field and publication year (see PathOS Indicator Handbook, Citation Impact Indicator³)
- **Patent citations**
- **Science-industry collaboration**
- **Gender authorship equity**

² https://handbook.pathos-project.eu/sections/2_academic_impact/thematic_persistence.html

³ https://handbook.pathos-project.eu/sections/2_academic_impact/citation_impact.html

- **Alignment with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**

By matching OA articles with statistically similar closed-access counterparts, for example, papers published in the same year, with comparable early citation counts, collaboration scale, and author characteristics, the study estimates the independent effects of each OA route between Green and Published. It thus moves beyond correlation, offering **causal evidence** on whether and how openness sustains emerging, socially relevant research directions.

3.1.2. Data and Tools in Practice

This case study employed an integrated data pipeline to evaluate the impact of Open Access routes on the persistence and influence of research topics in the AI-for-Climate literature. The workflow combined bibliometric enrichment, organizational metadata, gender classification, patent linkage, and topic-level modelling into a harmonized dataset suitable for indicator analysis and causal inference.

Data Sources

- **OpenAIRE Research Graph (August 2024):** Provided Open Access color coding (Green, Bronze, Hybrid, Gold, Diamond), license metadata, and affiliation details.
- **Semantic Scholar (April 2024):** Supplied citation counts, reference counts, and influential citation metrics.
- **ROR.org (October 2024):** Enabled classification of authors' institutional affiliations (e.g., whether the organizations listed in paper metadata were academic, industrial, or other).
- **PATSTAT (Spring 2024):** Delivered forward patent citation links from scientific publications.
- **SciNoBo Toolkit:** Supplied Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) tags, Field of Science (FoS) classification, Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI), and topic assignments.

Data sources, Tools and Functional Roles

Table 3: Data sources and tools used in the "Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence" case study

Data source / Tool	Functionality
OpenAIRE	Identified Open Access status and color, resolved affiliations, enriched metadata for repository-based and published OA classification.

Semantic Scholar	Retrieved citation metrics (total citations, influential citations, references), essential for early quality signals and impact estimation.
SciNoBo	Assigned SDG tags, FoS categories (L1–L6), topics, and FWCI; calculated topic persistence indicators.
PATSTAT	Provided forward citations from patents linked to publications via DOI, enabling analysis of industrial uptake.
ROR.org	Classified organizations by type (e.g., education, company), supporting science–industry collaboration detection.
Gender Classification Tool	<p>Parsed given names to infer gender and derive gender equity indicators (e.g., first/last authorship by women).</p> <p>Huggingface model used: padmajabfrl/Gender-Classification</p>
Custom Python Pipelines	Handled data integration, indicator construction, topic-level aggregation, and causal matching (PSM).

Indicator Construction

All indicators followed the specifications from the PathOS Indicator Handbook. The table below outlines each indicator and how it was derived:

Table 4: Indicators applied and their calculation details in the "Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence" case study

Indicator	Source(s)	Calculation Details
Open Access Status and Color	OpenAIRE	Resolved per article using isgreen, openaccesscolor, and isindiamondjournal metadata. Dual-mode OA and Bronze OA were excluded.

Citation Count	Semantic Scholar	Raw citation totals per article.
Influential Citations	Semantic Scholar	Citations from highly cited papers, used as a proxy for scholarly visibility.
FWCI (Field-Weighted Citation Impact)	SciNoBo	Normalized citation score, accounting for field and year.
Patent Citations	PATSTAT	Number of forward patent citations per article (DOI linkage).
Science-Industry Collaboration	ROR.org + OpenAIRE	Articles flagged if affiliated organizations included both a company and a non-commercial research actor.
Gender Equity	Gender Classification Tool	Calculated presence of women among first authors, last authors, and all-women author teams.
SDG Alignment	SciNoBo	Each publication is assigned SDG tags. For this case study, we derived: (a) Total SDG breadth (number of unique SDGs assigned to a paper); (b) Primary climate-AI SDG count (presence of SDGs 7, 11, 12, 13); (c) Secondary climate-AI SDG count (presence of SDGs 6, 9, 15); and (d) Total climate-AI SDG count (sum of primary and secondary).
Topic Persistence Score	SciNoBo + Custom Model	Computed from topic-year trajectories, growth rates, sequence duration, FWCI and recency. Applied to L5-level FoS topics.

Workflow Details

- **Corpus Filtering:** Started from a base of over 35 million articles; filtered to 132,134 AI-for-Climate publications (2010–2021) using SciNoBo topics and keyword logic.
- **Metadata Enrichment:** Applied OpenAIRE, Semantic Scholar, SciNoBo, PATSTAT, and gender tools to construct outcome variables.
- **Topic Attribution:** Mapped each article to its dominant L5 topic using SciNoBo's hierarchical taxonomy; calculated persistence scores for each topic and assigned them back to papers.
- **Matching Design:** Applied propensity-score matching (nearest-neighbour with 0.25 calliper, the standard rule-of-thumb bandwidth recommended in the literature to balance precision with sample retention) to create two balanced comparisons: Green OA vs Closed and Published OA vs Closed. Matching covariates included early citations, FWCI, authorship features, year, and collaboration scale.
- **Output Integration:** All matched samples and indicators were exported in Excel and Parquet formats for downstream analysis. Final outputs included (i) a **paper-level dataset** containing each publication enriched with all PathOS indicators (citations, FWCI, OA status, gender equity, etc.), and (ii) a **topic-level dataset** aggregating publications into SciNoBo's Field of Science (FoS) L5 topics, with persistence scores and topic trajectories over time. Both were exported in Excel and Parquet formats for re-use and analysis.

This multi-source, reproducible infrastructure enabled a high-resolution analysis of how specific Open Access pathways affect long-term knowledge dynamics in AI-for-Climate research.

3.1.3. Operational Observations & Lessons Learned

The implementation of this case study highlighted several practical and methodological challenges encountered when evaluating the long-term effects of Open Access practices on the persistence of AI-for-Climate research topics. The integration of multiple data sources, the reliance on DOIs as linking identifiers, and the use of automated classification tools introduced several complexities. This section reflects on these challenges, outlines the workarounds and adjustments applied during implementation, and distils broader insights for future Open Science evaluation efforts.

Data Quality and Consistency Issues

One of the most persistent challenges was inconsistency in metadata between platforms. Open Access status, for example, was classified differently across Semantic Scholar, OpenAIRE, and other sources. Semantic Scholar's OA flag was particularly unreliable for distinguishing between Green, Published, and ambiguous forms of openness. To mitigate this, the case study relied exclusively on OpenAIRE's OA classification fields (`bestaccessright`, `openaccesscolor`, and `isindiamondjournal`), which offered a more granular and authoritative distinction between OA types. This decision ensured alignment with the study's clean treatment definitions and improved the reliability of causal attribution.

Affiliation metadata also revealed inconsistencies. While OpenAIRE and ROR.org both provided valuable institutional information, differences in how organizations were named, formatted, or categorized led to mismatches. In particular, ROR's coverage was skewed toward academic and public-sector entities, with limited representation of private companies. This restricted the study's ability to fully capture science–industry collaboration, potentially underestimating that indicator's prevalence.

Measurement and Causal Logic Issues

A fundamental methodological concern was the ecological fallacy in topic persistence measurement. The study assigns each individual paper the persistence score of its broader topic, then compares papers with different OA strategies. However, topic persistence is inherently a group-level phenomenon - research topics persist, not individual papers. This creates a logical disconnect between the research question (whether OA strategies help individual papers achieve impact) and the measurement approach (whether individual papers happen to be in topics that later showed persistence). The causal chain from individual paper OA strategy to topic-level persistence remains unclear, as persistence scores reflect aggregate topic dynamics rather than individual paper characteristics.

Tool Limitations and Classification Errors

Several automated tools introduced classification errors or scope constraints. The SciNoBo toolkit's topic assignments and FWCI calculations proved generally reliable, but some misclassifications of subject area and topic boundaries did occur. Similarly, the Hugging Face gender classification model provided scalable author-gender inferences but was vulnerable to regional naming variations and occasionally failed to recognize non-binary or culturally ambiguous names.

More broadly, the combination of multiple tools increased the risk of error propagation. When a DOI was missing or malformed in one source, it could not be matched across the others. This reduced effective sample size and introduced selection bias. For instance, if a DOI from Semantic Scholar was not recognized in PATSTAT, the corresponding paper lacked patent citation data even if it had real-world industrial impact. The same issue affected SDG

assignments, topic persistence scores, and OA classification, where completeness depended on correct and consistent DOI resolution.

Temporal and Structural Biases

Time-dependence was another important limitation. Because citation accrual (especially from patents) is a lagging indicator, articles published later in the 2010–2021 window had less time to accumulate impact. This introduced a temporal bias, particularly for measures like topic persistence, FWCI, and patent citations. Although publication year was included as a covariate in the matching model, it could not fully compensate for the fact that some articles simply had fewer years to register influence. Similarly, coverage bias affected more recent or lower-profile publications that may not yet have been fully indexed across all platforms.

Workarounds and Adaptations

Several practical adaptations were made to stabilize the pipeline and enhance the robustness of the analysis:

- **Authoritative OA Resolution:** We replaced Semantic Scholar's OA flag with OpenAIRE's `bestaccessright` and `OA colour` fields, standardizing access status across all DOIs.
- **Fuzzy Affiliation Matching:** To mitigate inconsistencies in organization names across OpenAIRE and ROR.org, we implemented fuzzy string matching and normalization techniques. This allowed partial alignment of near-duplicate institutional entries and improved the accuracy of affiliation-type mappings, particularly for identifying industry partners in collaborative research outputs.
- **Robust Cleaning Pipeline:** We enforced strict data hygiene by dropping records with missing or infinite values on key variables and coercing all regression inputs to numeric types. This prevented silent type errors during estimation.
- **Manual Spot-Checks:** Although the core pipeline was automated, periodic manual reviews of random samples were conducted to verify DOI mappings, citance classifications, and affiliation assignments.
- **Post-matching Validation:** All covariates in the propensity score model were tested for balance using standardized mean differences. This helped confirm that residual differences in observable traits did not drive the estimated effects.

Insights for Future Evaluations

The lessons from this case study extend beyond AI-for-Climate and offer several takeaways for similar efforts:

- **Cross-platform integration is fragile.** Linking tools via DOIs is powerful but error-prone. Harmonization must be intentional, with cleaning, fallback strategies, and completeness checks at every stage.

- **Time-sensitive indicators need time-aware models.** Citation- and patent-based outcomes evolve slowly; even causal analyses must be interpreted in light of publication timing and field dynamics.
- **Classifier outputs need context.** Automated tools like gender detection and topic modeling offer scale but should be combined with spot checks and realistic thresholds to avoid overconfidence in noisy outputs.
- **Simplicity at the treatment level improves causal clarity.** By excluding ambiguous or overlapping OA cases, the study achieved cleaner contrasts and more interpretable results, highlighting a design choice that future evaluations should consider.

In sum, this case study demonstrated that meaningful and nuanced Open Science indicators can be built through the combination of multiple data sources and tools, provided that the workflow includes appropriate safeguards for quality, alignment, and causal interpretability. Despite limitations, the adapted pipeline proved capable of generating reliable estimates of long-term OS effects and offers a valuable foundation for replication and extension in other domains.

3.1.4. Reusability & Transferability

The **data pipeline** and **indicator framework** developed in this case study are **reusable** by teams interested in assessing the **long-term impact of Open Access practices**, particularly in **fast-moving** or **high-stakes domains** such as **AI**, **climate**, and **sustainability**. The setup is well suited for **national-level policy evaluations**, **institutional repository assessments**, and **thematic bibliometric studies**.

Reusing this framework requires access to **structured publication metadata** (for example, via **OpenAIRE**, **Semantic Scholar**, **PATSTAT**), **topic modelling capabilities** (such as **SciNoBo**), and **basic computational infrastructure** to apply enrichment scripts and matching algorithms. While the specific focus here was on **AI-for-Climate**, the approach can generalize to any domain where **topic-level persistence** and **differentiated OA routes** are of interest.

Beyond PathOS, elements of this setup are expected to support **continued monitoring of Open Science practices**, including potential **integration into institutional dashboards**, **funder evaluations**, and **follow-on studies** extending the behavioral-indicator framework to other disciplines and crises.

3.2. Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications

3.2.1. Purpose and Focus (brief)

This case study investigated whether observable Open Science behaviours, specifically, the referencing and reuse of research artifacts such as datasets and software, are associated with measurable downstream impact in the context of COVID-19-related research. It aimed to go beyond traditional binary definitions of openness (e.g., free-to-read) and instead evaluate **practical openness** through two behavioural proxies:

- **Traceability:** whether a publication clearly references external datasets or software, supporting transparency and verification;
- **Reusability:** whether a publication creates a dataset or software artifact that is explicitly reused and cited in subsequent research.

Using a regression-based design, the study explored whether these behaviours correlate with various forms of research impact, including:

- **Academic indicators:** citation volume, field-weighted citation impact, and interdisciplinarity;
- **Economic indicators:** forward citations from patents and evidence of industry–science collaboration;
- **Societal indicators:** citations from clinical trials and clinical guidelines;
- **Reproducibility signals:** polarity of mentions in citation statements (citations) (supporting, neutral, refuting).

The focus was on identifying not only whether these practices are linked to greater impact, but also under what conditions, such as paper quality, visibility, or timing during the pandemic, they are most effective. This makes the case study relevant for funders, infrastructure providers, and policy makers interested in assessing the **real-world consequences of Open Science behaviours**, particularly during high-pressure, high-volume research environments like a global health emergency.

3.2.2. Data and Tools in Practice

This case study used a multi-layered data architecture and analytical workflow to evaluate the impact of two Open Science behaviours: referencing and reuse of research artifacts. The process integrated bibliometric, clinical, patent, and organizational metadata with full-text mining and behavioural signal detection, resulting in a harmonized dataset for indicator analysis.

Data Sources

- **CORD-19 (June 2022):** Base corpus of COVID-19 publications.

- **OpenAIRE Research Graph (August 2024):** Affiliation metadata, Open Access classification, and organizational links.
- **Semantic Scholar (April 2024):** Citation/reference counts, full-text content, influential citations.
- **ROR.org (October 2024):** Enabled classification of authors' institutional affiliations (e.g., whether the organizations listed in paper metadata were academic, industrial, or other).
- **PATSTAT (Spring 2024):** Forward citations from patents linked to research publications.
- **PubMed (January 2025):** Metadata used to classify clinical trials and guidelines based on PMID-linked citations.

Data sources, Tools and Functional Roles

Table 5: Data sources and tools used in the "Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications" case study

Data source / Tool	Functionality
SciNoBo Toolkit	Performed full-text mining to detect references to datasets/software using the Research Artefact Analysis (RAA) tool, extracted citation statements (citances), classified polarity (e.g. supporting), intent (e.g. reuse), and semantics (e.g. artefact) of citations using the Citance Analysis (CA) tool. Also computed FWCI (Field-Weighted Citation Index), Field of Science (FoS), and interdisciplinarity.
OpenAIRE Graph + API	Identified Open Access status using fine-grained color coding (green, bronze, hybrid, gold, diamond); enriched affiliation data.
ROR.org	Classified organizations by type (e.g., education, company) to infer science-industry collaborations.
PATSTAT	Provided forward patent citations to evaluate technological and industrial impact.
PubMed + PMID Classifier	Enabled identification of citations from clinical trials and guidelines through publication type analysis.

Custom Python Pipelines	Handled data integration, filtering, deduplication, indicator construction, and output export for modelling.
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Indicator Calculation

All indicators were constructed according to the **PathOS Indicator Handbook** methodologies. The table below summarizes how each one was derived:

Table 6: Indicators applied and their calculation details in the "Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications" case study

Indicator	Source(s)	Calculation Details
Open Access (OA)	OpenAIRE API	Determined using bestaccessright and OA colour fields (green, bronze, hybrid, gold, diamond).
Citation Volume	Semantic Scholar	Total citation count per paper.
Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI)	SciNoBo	Normalized citation score accounting for field and year.
Interdisciplinarity (Macro/Meso)	SciNoBo	Calculated based on Field of Science (FoS) classifications.
Patent Citations	PATSTAT	Count of forward citations from patents to each publication (via DOI linkage).
Science-Industry Collaboration	OpenAIRE + ROR	Binary indicator: true if at least one "company" and one "science" org co-appear in affiliations.
Clinical Trial Citations	PubMed + Semantic Scholar	Number of citing papers classified as clinical trials.
Clinical Guideline Citations	PubMed + Semantic Scholar	Number of citing papers classified as guidelines.
Polarity of Mentions (Reproducibility Proxy)	SciNoBo	Citance-level classification: supporting, neutral, refuting.

Reuse of Artifacts (Reusability)	SciNoBo	Binary indicator: true if the paper received at least one “reuse-artifact” citance where a citing paper explicitly mentions reusing a dataset/software from the focal paper.
Artifact Count (Traceability)	SciNoBo	Count of named datasets/software referenced in the publication.

Workflow Details

1. **Corpus Filtering:** Limited the COVID-19 corpus to publications from 2020–2021 that both created at least one artifact and received at least one citation (N = 115,467).
2. **Behavioural Signal Extraction:**
 - **Traceability:** Measured by counting named datasets/software referenced in the paper’s full text.
 - **Reusability:** Inferred through structured citance analysis; papers receiving explicit "reuse" mentions to their artifacts were flagged via the “intent” classification of the citances.
3. **Enrichment:**
 - **SciNoBo:** Extracted artifacts, citance semantics, FWCI, interdisciplinarity, FoS codes.
 - **OpenAIRE API:** Refined OA status for each DOI.
 - **ROR Mapping:** Assigned affiliation types and derived industry–science collaboration flags.
 - **PubMed Parsing:** Identified citing articles classified as clinical trials or guidelines.
4. **Integration and Export:**
 - All indicators were merged into a master Dataframe and exported in Excel and Parquet formats.
 - This served as the input for the regression analysis described in Deliverable D3.3.

This multi-source, high-throughput infrastructure enabled reliable estimation of how specific Open Science practices influence real-world impact, with sufficient resolution to support both causal modelling and policy interpretation.

3.2.3. Operational Observations & Lessons Learned

The operationalization of Open Science indicators in this case study required the integration of diverse bibliometric, organizational, and textual data sources. While the analytical model successfully demonstrated measurable links between observable reuse and downstream impact, it also surfaced several challenges related to data quality, tool limitations, and integration complexity. This section reflects on those technical and methodological challenges, documents key adaptations made during implementation, and distils insights for future applications.

Data Quality and Inconsistencies

A recurrent challenge was inconsistency in metadata across sources. One prominent example was the **Open Access status**, which was represented differently by various platforms. We observed that Semantic Scholar's OA flag lacked sufficient granularity and was prone to classification noise. To address this, we relied instead on **OpenAIRE's authoritative access classification**, using both the `bestaccessright` and `OA colour` fields to standardize access status across all DOIs in the study. This allowed for a more nuanced and reliable assessment of openness in line with FAIR principles.

Affiliation metadata also exhibited occasional inconsistencies. Differences between **OpenAIRE** and **ROR.org** in how institutional affiliations were named, formatted, or classified affected the detection of science–industry collaborations. For example, some organizations appeared under slightly different names or were missing from one registry but present in another. These mismatches required additional validation steps and, in some cases, conservative exclusions to ensure correct alignment of affiliation data across tools and to maintain the reliability of industry involvement indicators.

Coverage Gaps and Scope Limitations

Several data sources exhibited structural limitations in their scope and coverage:

- **ROR.org**, while critical for determining the nature of contributing institutions, is optimized for academic and public-sector organizations. Private-sector entities were frequently underrepresented, making it harder to detect industry involvement and potentially leading to an underestimation of cross-sector collaboration indicators.
- **PATSTAT** provided high-quality linkage between publications and patent citations but lacked coverage of informal or non-patent-based innovation pathways. Moreover, the

citation lag inherent to patent documentation introduced a temporal bias that penalized newer publications.

- **Clinical trial and guideline citations**, used to signal medical uptake, are also delayed indicators that accrue slowly over time. Papers published later in the pandemic (e.g. 2021) had less opportunity to be cited in such documents, potentially suppressing clinical impact estimates for more recent research.

Tool Limitations and Semantic Classification Issues

The automated detection of reuse behaviours relied heavily on classifier models, particularly those embedded in **SciNoBo**. While the tool enabled scalable classification of citation contexts, it was not immune to **misclassifications**. These included both false positives, citances flagged as reuse that did not imply direct application of a dataset or software, and false negatives, where valid reuse references were missed.

Such misclassifications can distort impact estimates, especially in causal models where treatment status (i.e. reuse) is a key explanatory variable. Since classifier outputs drive binary distinctions used in regression modelling, even modest classification errors may propagate into biased effect estimates. Recognizing this risk, we implemented both statistical and procedural mitigations, discussed below.

More fundamentally, the study measures documented reuse through citation mentions rather than actual reuse behaviour. Extensive unreported reuse may occur where researchers use datasets or software without formally citing the source, while receiving a reuse citation may reflect citing authors' documentation practices rather than the artifact's true utility. This creates a measurement validity gap between the theoretical construct (actual reuse) and the operational indicator (documented reuse citations). Moreover, the study conflates reusability (inherent artifact characteristics that facilitate reuse) with observed reuse (downstream citations mentioning reuse). This means the analysis tests whether artifacts that happened to receive reuse citations show different impact patterns, rather than whether artifacts with superior reusability characteristics generate more impact.

Dependency Chains and Error Propagation

A core complexity arose from the **high dependency on DOIs as linking keys** across datasets. Datasets such as OpenAIRE Graph, Semantic Scholar, PATSTAT, and ROR all use DOIs as identifiers, but not always as their primary identifier. Thus, any missing, malformed, or mismatched DOI could sever the connection between data sources.

This issue led to **error propagation** in downstream stages. For instance, if a DOI was not recognized by PATSTAT, no patent citation data could be retrieved, even if the paper was reused industrially. Similarly, missing DOIs in OpenAIRE affected OA classification and affiliation

mapping. These dependencies reduced the effective sample size and introduced potential selection bias.

Workarounds and Adaptations

To address these challenges and stabilize the pipeline, the following workarounds and adaptations were implemented:

- **Authoritative OA Resolution:** We replaced Semantic Scholar's OA flag with OpenAIRE's bestaccessright and OA colour fields, standardizing access status across all DOIs.
- **Fuzzy Affiliation Matching:** To mitigate inconsistencies in organization names across OpenAIRE and ROR.org, we implemented fuzzy string matching and normalization techniques. This allowed partial alignment of near-duplicate institutional entries and improved the accuracy of affiliation-type mappings, particularly for identifying industry partners in collaborative research outputs.
- **Design-Based Filtering:** To reduce noise from low-visibility papers, our regression sample included only publications that (1) created at least one dataset/software artifact and (2) received at least one citation. This removed edge cases where reuse signals could not meaningfully accrue.
- **Robust Cleaning Pipeline:** We enforced strict data hygiene by dropping records with missing or infinite values on key variables and coercing all regression inputs to numeric types. This prevented silent type errors during estimation.
- **Manual Spot-Checks:** Although the core pipeline was automated, periodic manual reviews of random samples were conducted to verify DOI mappings, citance classifications, and affiliation assignments.

Insights for Similar Future Efforts

This case study provides several transferable insights for future Open Science evaluations:

- **Inter-tool alignment is fragile but essential.** Identifier mismatches and schema differences between tools must be anticipated and actively managed through rigorous validation steps.
- **Classifier-based reuse detection is promising but sensitive.** Automated detection of Open Science behaviours such as reuse offers scale, but classification performance must be carefully assessed and, where possible, supported by human-in-the-loop verification.
- **Citation-based indicators are inherently time-dependent.** Translational and clinical uptake can take years to materialize; indicator interpretation must adjust accordingly, especially for policy-facing applications.

- **Open science behaviors can be captured in structured, measurable ways**, but doing so requires not just data access but deliberate methodological design, quality control, and context-aware modelling.

Together, these lessons reinforce the value of rigorous, behaviourally grounded Open Science evaluation. While technical hurdles remain, the demonstrated feasibility of the approach signals a promising direction for ongoing methodological refinement and wider application.

3.2.4. Reusability & Transferability

The setup developed in this case study is **reusable by other teams** aiming to evaluate the **downstream impact of Open Science behaviours**, especially those involving **dataset or software reuse**. It is most applicable in contexts where access to **large-scale publication metadata**, full-text corpora, and citation relationships is available, such as **national-level research assessments, institutional Open Science monitoring, or thematic studies** in high-impact domains like health, AI, or climate.

Reuse requires access to **structured citation and affiliation metadata** (for example, via **OpenAIRE Graph, Semantic Scholar**, or similar), **computational infrastructure** for full-text mining, and capacity to apply or adapt classifiers like **SciNoBo** for artifact detection and citance parsing.

Notably, the core data sources and tools used in this study (**SciNoBo, OpenAIRE Graph, Semantic Scholar, ROR.org**, and **PATSTAT**) were also applied across **other PathOS case studies**, demonstrating their **transferability across contexts** and their value in supporting **comparable workflows**. This shared infrastructure reinforces their potential for **broader adoption in future Open Science evaluations**.

Beyond PathOS, elements of this setup are expected to support **continued monitoring of Open Science practices**, including potential **integration into institutional dashboards, funder evaluations**, and **follow-on studies** extending the behavioural-indicator framework to other disciplines and crises.

3.3. ELIXIR's Bioinformatics Resources

3.3.1. Purpose and Focus (brief)

The Bioinformatics case study aimed to demonstrate the long-term benefits and socioeconomic value generated by the industry's use of ELIXIR's open bioinformatic resources. ELIXIR is The primary focus was on understanding how these resources drive innovation in the life sciences and uncovering broader impacts that may have gone unnoticed.

The case study covers the areas of Open Infrastructure and Open Innovation within Open Science, with a particular emphasis on the life sciences and their academic and economic impacts. It builds upon ELIXIR's existing impact assessment practices, leveraging metrics on academic and economic impact regarding citations, academic-industry collaboration, and innovation outputs to provide concrete evidence of high-level impacts.

3.3.2. Data and Tools in Practice

In this case study, we used a diversity of data and tools for each topic we worked on. The table below presents each of them.

Table 7: Data sources, tools, and indicators used in the "ELIXIR Bioinformatics Resources" case study

Topic	Datasets	Tools	Impact
ELIXIR-supported publications	Publications are monthly extracted by EuroPMC (semi-manual extraction procedure), and enriched with Semantic Scholar, ROR.org (link)	SciNoBo, and manual analysis of trends	Academic indicators (Citation impact and Extra-academic collaborations)
<p>For the ELIXIR-supported publications, the SciNoBo tools (as mentioned in other sections) provided information on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field of Science (FoS) that helped understand the areas of scientific area, • Citation indexes (Field-Weighted Citation Impact and influential citation count) that evaluated the breadth of impact to the research fields • Affiliations, based on which we identified the publications with industry affiliations and see the topics where public-private collaborations take place productively 			
Bioinformatics skills in academia and in industry	Links to the job vacancies advertised in the ELIXIR job vacancy portal between Jan to July 2024 (link)	Manual text mining of eleven bioinformatic skills found	Economic impact (Labour market)
<p>The description of the job vacancies was extracted in word formats and an expert went through the text and tried to identify if any of the selected bioinformatic skills were mentioned. Each job vacancy was also marked if it was within academia or industry.</p>			
Patents that reference ELIXIR resources or ELIXIR-supported publications	Patent documents are extracted monthly from Lens.org. This information was enriched with information from PatStat (link)	Manual analysis of trends	Economic impact (Innovation output, public-private collaborations)

The PatStat provided information on:

- Technology fields of these patent documents which showed us the sectors that we have impacted, and IPC Codes (International Patent Classification codes associated with each patent) and CPC Codes (Cooperative Patent Classification codes)
- Applicants' and inventors' affiliation, country and sectors that indicated:
 - The impact on multiple countries' inventions,
 - The level of industrial usage of the ELIXIR open resources in inventions,
 - The intersectoral or cross-border collaborations
 - The level of dependency of some specific companies on these open resources
- Citation number of these patents that showcase highly impactful patents that used ELIXIR open resources and trends among the different technological fields and intersectoral or cross-border collaborations

Our publications and patent dataset were enriched by the ARC team recurring to the following tools:

- **Semantic Scholar (April 2024):** Supplied citation counts, reference counts, and influential citation metrics.
- **ROR.org (October 2024):** Enabled classification of affiliated organizations (e.g., academia, industry).
- **PATSTAT (Spring 2024):** Delivered forward patent citation links from scientific publications.
- **SciNoBo Toolkit:** Supplied Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) tags, Field of Science (FoS) classification, Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI), and topic assignments.

Data sources, Tools and Functional Roles

Table 8: Data sources, tools and their functional roles in the "ELIXIR Bioinformatics Resources" case study

Data source / Tool	Functionality
Semantic Scholar	Retrieved citation metrics (total citations, influential citations, references), essential for early quality signals and impact estimation.
SciNoBo	Assigned SDG tags, FoS categories (L1–L6), topics, and FWCI; calculated topic persistence indicators.
PATSTAT	Provided forward citations from patents linked to publications via DOI, enabling analysis of industrial uptake.
ROR.org	Classified organizations by type (e.g., education, company), supporting science–industry collaboration detection.

The resulting dataset (csv file) was then analyzed by the ELIXIR team recurring to Excel.

3.3.3. Operational Observations & Lessons Learned

The primary challenge for ELIXIR is tracking the usage of its Open Data resources, which require neither registration nor payment. To address this common issue, ELIXIR has developed a series of procedures to assess impact. These procedures involve a monthly, semi-manual curation of information, as mentioned in the previous session.

In this case study, we focused on gathering additional information from diverse and previously unused sources, such as SciNoBo, Semantic Scholar, ROR.org and PATSTAT. We relied on the expertise of PathOS partners, who were knowledgeable about these sources. Their willingness to understand our case study and their dedication enabled us to collect a wide range of new information. This data was then analysed within the case study, revealing useful trends that allow us to make impact statements for ELIXIR's open resources.

The technical expertise required for SciNoBo and the extraction of information from PATSTAT may limit our ability to repeat this work using these sources. However, the patent indicator and the information extracted from Lens.org have been integrated into the ELIXIR dashboard, thanks to the expertise developed during the PathOS project. Additionally, identifying industry authors in publications and inventors in patents has been incorporated into ELIXIR's methodology for processing impact indicators.

3.3.4. Reusability & Transferability

Overall, the methodology developed during this case study can be easily reused by other ELIXIR members and Research Infrastructures. However, it does require technical expertise in using the variety of datasets and tools to extract the specific information needed.

After the end of the project, ELIXIR will produce an impact report that will showcase all the impact conclusions derived from the PathOS project. This report will enable us to effectively communicate these conclusions to our members, funders, and other Research Infrastructures and share our lessons learned. It will also highlight the potential impact if more effort is invested in this often-overlooked topic.

3.4. Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP

3.4.1. Purpose and Focus

The RCAAP case study focuses on estimating the potential effects of depositing publications in Open Access Repositories (Green Open Access) aggregated by the RCAAP infrastructure. The

publications meeting the criteria outlined above were sourced from the OpenAIRE Graph. The OpenAIRE Graph includes a broader range of research outputs—such as master's dissertations and PhD theses from repositories—that often reflect collaborations with industry and other sectors and may not be found in commercial databases, which made it particularly suitable for our analysis. A tool to extract country-related publications from the OpenAIRE Graph has been developed as follows.

3.4.2. Data and Tools in Practice

Country-Specific Research Output Extraction Tool

In the context of the OpenAIRE Graph and related data infrastructure, the ability to identify and extract research results associated with a specific country is essential for monitoring scientific production, understanding national and international collaborations, and enabling targeted analytics. This functionality supports stakeholders such as funders, policy makers, research institutions, and infrastructure providers who need to evaluate research output and collaboration patterns at national and institutional levels.

To fulfil this requirement, a dedicated Spark-based processing component was developed. This tool scans the OpenAIRE metadata records and filters research outputs based on their geographical relation to a given country.

Requirement Specification

Objective

Develop a Spark-based application capable of:

- Parsing OpenAIRE-formatted metadata
- Identifying and extracting publications published in a given time frame that
 - Are affiliated to at least one organization in the specified country
 - Have been funded by a funder whose jurisdiction is the specified country
 - Have the specified country listed in their metadata fields.
- Extending the identified results based on the three criteria listed above with
 - Linked organization related information
 - Project funding related information
 - A flag indicating if the result is provided by a data source present in a given list
- Return all the extended results in a csv file

CSV file specification

The following table lists the field in the produced csv, also describing their type and semantics

Table 9: CSV file field specification for country-specific research output extraction

Name	Type	Description
id	String	Unique identifier of the publication (e.g., result____:abc123def456)
type	String	Type of the publication (e.g., journal article, dataset)
originalid	String	Original identifiers (e.g., DOI, Handle), excluding internal ones
mainTitle	String	Main title of the publication
subTitle	String	Subtitle of the publication, if available
author	String	Full names of the authors, separated by "; "
author_pid	String	Persistent identifiers of authors (e.g., ORCID), formatted as type::value
bestAccessRight	String	Overall access class (e.g., OPEN, RESTRICTED)
country	String	ISO country codes associated with the publication (e.g., PT, ES)
description	String	Abstract or description of the publication
embargoEndDate	String	Embargo end date (format: YYYY-MM-DD), if applicable
citationClass	String	Qualitative impact class, if available
citationCount	Double	Number of citations (e.g., altmetrics count)

downloads	Integer	Number of downloads
views	Integer	Number of views
accessRight	String	Access types from instances (e.g., OPEN, CLOSED), comma-separated
alternateIdentifier	String	Alternate identifiers, comma-separated
license	String	License (e.g., CC-BY, CC0) as declared in instances
language	String	ISO code of the publication's language (e.g., en)
pid	String	Persistent identifiers (type::value), comma-separated
publicationYear	String	Year of publication or acceptance
publisher	String	Name of the publisher
FoSLevel1	String	Field of Science level 1 codes (e.g., 01, 03), separated by ";"
FoSLevel2	String	Field of Science level 2 codes (e.g., 0101, 0302)
FoSLevel3	String	Field of Science level 3 codes (e.g., 010101)
FoSLevel4	String	Field of Science level 4 codes (e.g., 01010101)
green	Boolean	true if the publication is available via Green Open Access
inDiamondJournal	Boolean	true if published in a Diamond Open Access journal

openAccessColor	String	Open Access color (e.g., gold, bronze, hybrid)
RCAAPRepo	Boolean	true if hosted in at least one of the specified repositories

This functionality has been applied on data associated with the country Portugal and using the RCAAP data sources as the list of repositories to check for presence in the selected publications. The specified time range covers publications from 2014 (excluded) up to and including 2024.

This tool satisfies a core data extraction requirement within the OpenAIRE infrastructure, enabling country-based filtering of research outputs. Its design leverages Spark for scalability and efficiency and supports integration into national and institutional monitoring workflows.

The resulting dataset was then enriched by the ARC team recurring to the following tools:

- **Semantic Scholar (April 2024):** Supplied citation counts, reference counts, and influential citation metrics.
- **ROR.org (October 2024):** Enabled classification of affiliated organizations (e.g., academia, industry).
- **PATSTAT (Spring 2024):** Delivered forward patent citation links from scientific publications.
- **SciNoBo Toolkit:** Supplied Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) tags, Field of Science (FoS) classification, Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI), and topic assignments.

Data sources, Tools and Functional Roles

Table 10: Data sources and tools used in the "Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP" case study

Data source / Tool	Functionality
OpenAIRE	Identified Open Access status and colour, resolved affiliations, enriched metadata for repository-based and published OA classification.
Semantic Scholar	Retrieved citation metrics (total citations, influential citations, references), essential for early quality signals and impact estimation.
SciNoBo	Assigned SDG tags, FoS categories (L1–L6), topics, and FWCI; calculated topic persistence indicators.

PATSTAT	Provided forward citations from patents linked to publications via DOI, enabling analysis of industrial uptake.
ROR.org	Classified organizations by type (e.g., education, company), supporting science–industry collaboration detection.

The resulting dataset (csv file) was then analysed by the UMinho team recurring to Excel.

3.4.3. Operational Observations & Lessons Learned

RCAAP repositories include a diverse range of publication types, such as reports, master dissertations, and PhD theses. The metadata for these outputs, although curated by institutional repository managers, is more heterogenous and lacks the level of standardisation found in other publishing venues, which makes it more difficult to analyse.

These outputs also traditionally receive fewer citations than peer-reviewed journal articles, and as such there are some challenges while performing an analysis using traditional bibliometric indicators. Applying standard bibliometric indicators (like citation counts or impact factors) to assess the impact is more complex and may not accurately reflect their value or influence.

Tracking and measuring collaborations with companies and industry is challenging, largely due to inconsistent authorship attribution for non-academic contributors and the lack of persistent identifiers—such as ROR IDs—for companies in metadata records. Bridging this gap will require enhanced metadata standards and stronger incentives to promote transparent authorship practices.

3.4.4. Reusability & Transferability

The methodology developed in this case study is adaptable and can be applied by other research infrastructures or funding bodies. However, its effective use depends on having the technical expertise to navigate and utilize diverse datasets and tools to extract and process the required information.

3.5. Effects of Data Repositories on Data Usage

3.5.1. Purpose and Focus

With our data citations and data mentions study, we aimed to understand the processes of sharing, using and reusing Open Data. In particular, we were interested in the role of data

repositories (Liaw, 2021) and the potential effects that the data repository where data is shared can have on subsequent reuse. This is already a known effect for published articles and relevant citations. In our study, we conducted analyses and interviews to understand whether this effect exists also in citations and/or mentions of data repositories.

3.5.2. Data and Tools in Practice

DATA CITATIONS ANALYSIS

We rely on DataCite¹ to establish links between datasets and publications, on the basis of related DOI that are coded as `IsSupplementTo`². We rely on OpenAlex for metadata about publications of which the datasets are supplements. In total, there are 4.145.337 supplement relationships, of which 3.381.247 refer to DOIs included in OpenAlex. Unfortunately, there are many datasets that indicate they are supplements to multiple publications. For our purpose, having multiple publications is not suitable, since it is then not clear which publication that dataset was introduced in. We therefore limit to datasets that have only a single unique DOI that is included in OpenAlex, which reduces this to 278.922 datasets. Note that one publication can introduce multiple datasets.

We retrieved the Global Data Citation Corpus (GDCC) from <https://zenodo.org/records/13376773> to analyse citations to datasets. We restricted the analysis to the 278.922 datasets that are supplements to unique publications in OpenAlex. It appears that many of the “citations” in GDCC are coded as `IsSupplementTo` in DataCite. We therefore decided to remove those “citations”, assuming here that DataCite is correct, and that GDCC is incorrect in labelling these “citations”. Of course, it is possible that our assumption is incorrect, and this is something that should be further cleaned in the future. After removing the supplement relations, we end up with only 3.259 citations for the 278.922 datasets.

Given the very low number of citations, it did not make much sense to analyse the number of citations. Instead, we therefore focused on whether a paper was cited or not. In total, there were 2.947 works cited, leaving 246.300 without any citations. Our dataset includes 185 distinct repositories, 5.973 different journals across 2.809 different fields published between 2000 and 2023.

We use Bayesian logistic regression, with

$$c_i \sim \text{bernoulli} \left(\text{logit}^{-1} \left(\alpha + \beta_{f_i}^F + \beta^J j_i + \beta_{y_i}^Y + \beta_{r_i}^R \right) \right),$$

while enforcing sum-to-zero constraints on all β parameters, where c_i is whether dataset i was cited or not, f_i the field, j_i the journal, y_i the publication year of the publication and r_i the repository where dataset i was stored. We set priors on each individual β so that the marginal prior distribution is a standard normal distribution³.

DATA MENTIONS ANALYSIS

In our data mentions study, we have sampled 200 publications from 2017, 2018 and 2019 from Scopus from categories in All Science Journal Classification Codes (ASJC) that fall under SSH (according to Scopus). We explicitly chose relatively recent years in order to increase the chances of data being reused. We manually extracted data mentions from full-text publications based on a fixed protocol.

Two individuals extracted data mentions independently according to the following protocol, and one of the individuals integrated and cleaned both extractions. The protocol was as follows:

1. Search for keywords in the article. Keywords searched for: Data; Reference; Repository; Survey; Identifier; Statistic; Observation; Experiment; Archive.
2. Scan the methodology section to see if there are any details provided on what data is being used.
3. Scan the references to see if anything “looks like” it might be a reference to a dataset.
4. Scan the footnotes for mentions of datasets.

The extracted data mentions were recorded in a spreadsheet, using a single sentence for each case, recording the page number², the full sentence in which the data was mentioned, the location (in-text/footnote/caption), the reused dataset(s), and associated references or identifiers, if any. Finally, we also aimed to record the reused dataset repository. No data mentioned in our dataset ever used a known data repository (e.g. as included in RE3Data³). We instead kept track of broader organisations, such as national bureau of statistics or public institutes, that might host multiple datasets. However, there is some ambiguity around these concepts, which we do need to take into account when studying the results.

The PDFs for these 162 publications were then processed by Datastet and SciNoBo to extract data mentions algorithmically. Not all PDFs could be processed, and only 154 of the 162 publications were processed successfully by Datastet and only 159 by SciNoBo. It should be noted though that these tools were able to also extract data mentions from non-English literature, but that we did not include because we did not extract data mentions manually from those publications. These tools provide an indication of whether data is reused, the page and sentence in which the data is mentioned, and the dataset itself. These tools do not automatically extract references linked to the dataset, nor extract the repository explicitly.

For both Datastet and SciNoBo algorithms, we only consider data mentions that are inferred to indicate data use, that is, we exclude data mentions that are inferred to indicate data sharing or data creation. Because there may be typographical differences in the extraction (e.g. including or excluding line-breaking hyphens), or slightly smaller or larger parts of sentences that were extracted, we used a string similarity to determine whether a sentence or data mention should be considered a match between the manual extraction and the algorithmic extraction. We used Python's `difflib.SequenceMatcher` to calculate the similarity. We manually evaluated the accuracy of the similarity and found that a similarity of 0.8 at the sentence level was most reasonable, while a similarity of 0.4 at the mention level, conditional upon the sentences matching, was most reasonable.

When comparing the manually extracted data mentions to the algorithmically extracted data mentions, we discern three levels: the document level, the sentence level, and the individual mention level. At the document level, we compared whether a document was labelled as having any data mentions. At the sentence level, we compared whether the same sentence was identified as having any data mentions. This relies on the string similarity as explained above. At the data mention level, we compare whether the algorithmically extracted data mention matches any of the manually extracted elements: the dataset itself, the identifier, the reference or the repository.

We only compared results for documents that have been manually labelled and processed by the respective algorithm. Since SciNoBo did not process 3 PDFs that Datastet did process, there is a slightly different baseline for the comparisons.

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

In our qualitative study, we reached out to networks that foster the sharing, use and reuse of Open Data, and asked for participants for our interview study. We first made sure our plan aligned with our internal ethics committee review. Then we prepared a consent form and an application form for the interview. After that, we put together an interview plan that would allow us to conduct the interview in a structured manner. The interviews were conducted and recorded on Microsoft Teams, and then transcribed for study purposes.

Interview Plan: Data Reuse Practices

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Check whether participant received and signed the consent form.
- Obtain consent for recording, only for purpose of transcribing interview. Without consent, we will just take notes / transcribe manually.
- Briefly introduce yourself, your research, and the purpose of the interview.

The goal of the case study: To understand better how data repositories affect data reuse. We are interested in understanding how people come to reuse data for

research, and if data repositories have any effect on whether data is reused or not. For example, data repositories may play a role in the visibility of certain datasets, or data repositories may have a certain reputation, leading people to trust datasets from such a repository.

We broadly define data as any evidence of phenomena for the purpose of research. This may range from spreadsheets or databases to text corpora or interview transcripts.

Data repositories are usually understood as repositories where researchers have deposited research data (openly). We here take a broader view, and also consider official government platforms, bureaus of statistics or data from NGOs or IGOs, since data in the social sciences often seem to come from these data sources.

- Outline the structure of the interview and reassure them about confidentiality and data usage.

2. Background Information (5 minutes)

- “Can you describe your current role and area of research in a few sentences?”
- “How long have you been working in this field?”
- “Can you briefly describe what data you typically use in your research?”

3. Current Data Reuse Practices (20 minutes)

- “Can you describe one example of how you reused a dataset for research?”
- “Can you describe how you typically access data for your research?”
 - Offer the interviewee the possibility to demonstrate something.
- “How do you find datasets created by others?”
 - Through personal connections
 - Through journal publications
 - Through data repositories
 - ...
- “Can you name some data repositories that you are familiar with?”
- “Do you visit data repositories to find data for your research?”
- “How do you evaluate the quality or reliability of datasets shared by others?”
- “Are there some data repositories you consider more reliable or trustworthy?”

4. Challenges and Opportunities (15 minutes)

- “Have you encountered any difficulties when trying to find data to reuse in your research?”
- “Have you encountered any challenges when trying to reuse data for research?”

- “Are there particular formats, standards, or metadata that make it easier for you to reuse data for research?”
- “Did data repositories help you find or reuse data for research?”
- “What could make the process of finding or reusing data for research easier?”

5. Closing (5 minutes)

- “Is there anything else I haven’t asked about that you want to share?”
- Thank the participant for their time and insights.
- Ask if they have any additional thoughts or questions.

3.5.3. Operational Observations & Lessons Learned

In the data citations study, we relied on Global Data Citation Corpus; however, this dataset focusses mostly on the biomedical domain, while we originally had a particular interest in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). There are scant data citations, such as those indexed in Datacite or Crossref, and the Global Data Citation Corpus (Datacite, 2024), focus mostly on the biomedical domain, and can therefore not be used to analyse the SSH. For this reason, we also analyse to what extent data citations can be automatically extracted from the literature in a second study.

In our qualitative study, we had difficulty finding participants interested and available for an interview appointment. Several announcements and emails in different networks have so far brought us three participants. Since the project has run out of time, for future efforts perhaps it would be more practical to announce the interview study earlier in the project timeline so that there is more time to gather participants. Another option could be directly contacting researchers for an interview, instead of asking them to contact us if they are interested. Another approach could be to send an interview invitation prior to a large-scale conference on relevant topics, and then schedule shorter interview slots during the conference, eliminating the scheduling efforts some academic may be avoiding due to heavy workload.

3.5.4. Reusability & Transferability

Our study setup and methodology can be reused by others in relevant contexts. Our study of data mentions should prove useful for researchers aiming to build more accurate algorithms. Similarly, our study design around citations of the global data citation corpus should prove useful for future studies around data citations. If we find more participants for our interview study, we will continue working on that aspect of our study.

3.6. French Open Access Infrastructure

3.6.1. Purpose and Focus

Based on previous, smaller-scaled studies conducted by the French Ministry for Higher Education and Research⁴, the case study led by the Centre for Internet and Society⁵ of the French National Centre for Scientific research (CNRS) aims at exploring the connection logs to the French Open Science platforms HAL⁶ and OpenEdition⁷.

A connection log is a massive text file that records all connection attempts made to a specific website. Depending on the server's configuration, it can store various kind of information about the resource that is being accessed and the user that accesses it. Log files can later be cleaned, enriched and aggregated to gain insight into the access to and the usage of a specific website.

⁴ *Umberto* (https://analytics.huma-num.fr/OpenEditionLab/umberto_oe/) and *Usages Alpha* (<https://lab.hypotheses.org/category/etude-sur-les-usages-des-lecteurs>) projects

⁵ <https://cis.cnrs.fr/en/>

⁶ <https://hal.science/>

⁷ <https://www.openedition.org/>

ACCESS, USE, IMPACT

Figure 1 From access to usage to impact

The digital availability of scientific resources is the precondition for Open Science to be accessed, used and impactful. "Open Science", in the sense used in most policy documents, is not possible without digital platforms, which are the meeting point between demand and supply for science and the analytical starting point for any further modelisation and study of the impact of Open Science. Our case study is therefore a study of access, based on logs. As shown in Figure 1, we differentiate access from use and from impact.

THE PLATFORMS

HAL⁸ is an archiving platform covering all scientific fields where researchers affiliated with at least one or several public or private academic institution can share their research outputs. Those can be of several types (articles, scientific communications, theses, preprints, software, dictionary entries...) although the vast majority of shared outputs are articles and theses. They can be published or not, and be of any Open Access "colour" – we will return to this notion and how we implemented it in the case study further below. Up-to-date, real-time statistics about the HAL platform can be found here⁹.

⁸ <https://about.hal.science/>

⁹ <https://monitor.hal.science/?gate=hal>

OpenEdition¹⁰ describes itself as “a comprehensive electronic publishing infrastructure dedicated to scholarly communication in the humanities and social sciences”. It is divided into four services: OpenEdition Journals, OpenEdition Books, Hypothèses (research blogs), and Calenda (scientific events). We analysed the connection logs to OpenEdition Journals, which hosts 661 online, peer-reviewed scholarly journals, some of which also have a simultaneous print edition. All resources available on OpenEdition are openly accessible. A very small share of them (>2%) are embargoed for a short amount of time (6 months to one year).

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Operating at platform level, we decided to try to answer following questions :

1. **Who** accesses OS platforms? What type of users access Open Science platforms? **Where** do those users live? Beyond the somewhat vague typology of societal, academic and economic users, can we classify them into a more detailed, rigorous and widely accepted **sectoral typology** using techniques that can be applied to large datasets?
2. **What** kind of resources are being accessed? What scientific field do the resources belong to?
3. Does the **openness status** of a resource have a positive or a negative effect on its likelihood to be accessed?
4. Is this effect always the same depending on those three **confounding factors**: the sectoral typology of users (Nace category¹¹), their geographical location, and the scientific field of the resources?

OPEN ACCESS DEFINITION AND OPEN ACCESS “COLOURS”

There are many ways of defining Open Access. The classification of Open Access into “colours” provides a useful starting point for both pedagogical and communication purposes, but it can also lead to confusion because it mixes several typological criteria in a sometimes inconsistent way¹². The definition given by the PathOS handbook¹³ is a good starting point, but we have needed to adapt it since reasoning in terms of “colours” takes into account factors that are not considered in our case study :

- First, colours define the Open Access status at the *journal level* rather than at the *publication level*. For example, the colour “hybrid” refers to an Open Access article published in a journal that also contains closed access articles.
- Second, colours consider *licensing*. For example, the colour “bronze” indicates an article that is free to read on the publisher’s website but lacks a clear license.
- Third, in some cases, colours include the *allocation of publishing costs*. For example, the category gold indicates that the author bears part of the publishing costs through article

¹⁰ <https://www.openedition.org/10918>

¹¹ The NACE is the industry standard classification system used in the European Union. This will be explained further below.

¹² As this Venn diagram tries to summarize for instance : https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Open_Access_colours_Venn.svg

¹³ https://handbook.pathos-project.eu/sections/1_open_science/prevalence_open_access_publishing.html

- processing charges (APCs)¹⁴.
- Fourth, colours take into account the *publication stage* (preprint, postprint, publisher's version). For example, gold and diamond Open Access articles correspond to the publisher's version of record.

For the purposes of our analysis, the question can be reduced to a single criterion: when a user accesses a resource on HAL or OpenEdition, can they obtain the full content without paying—irrespective of the license type, the publication stage, or the allocation of publishing costs? If the answer is yes, the resource is considered open; if the answer is no, it is considered closed.

On a practical level, we get this information from the OpenAlex database, which offers a range of variables describing the openness of resource. Those variables are subkeys of the *open_access* object¹⁵ :

- *oa_status*, a “colour-based” definition, with the limits pointed above, plus the fact that “as soon as there's a publisher-hosted copy (bronze, hybrid, or gold), *oa_status* is set to that publisher-hosted status”, which could end up in incoherent results (a resource can be available as a pre-print on HAL while its editors final version can be for-pay; although it's considered open based on our criteria, it would be marked as closed).
- *any_repository_has_fulltext* : a boolean specifying if, amongst all the locations of this resource, at least one Open Access repository contains the full text.
- *is_oa* : a boolean specifying if the given URL allows to read the full text of this work without needing to pay money or log in. This is the information we have retained for our case study.

CONFOUNDING FACTORS

Our method, which will be presented in detail below, enriches the logs by adding information about the “accessing” users and the “accessed” resources. We know the NACE class and geolocation of users; we know the openness status and discipline of resources. We treat NACE class, geolocation, and discipline as potential confounders¹⁶, since one of our objectives is to *isolate the causal effect of Open Access availability on the number of views a resource receives, while holding all other factors constant*.

Following figure shows the causal chain, the confounding factors and the corresponding handbook entries.

¹⁴ https://handbook.pathos-project.eu/sections/1_open_science/APC_costs.html

¹⁵ <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/works/work-object#the-openaccess-object>

¹⁶ See here for more detail : https://handbook.pathos-project.eu/sections/0_causality/causal_intro/article/intro-causality.html#confounders-colliders-and-mediators

Figure 2 Confounding factors, causal chain and corresponding handbook entries

3.6.2. Data and Tools in Practice

HIGH-LEVEL OVERVIEW OF TOOLS AND DATASETS USED

Following is a synoptic of the full data processing pipeline, along with publicity status of the used input and output data and the different tools used to process them.

In the spirit of Open Science, we designed our method to rely on international standards and widely used Open Source tools. We hope that this will allow our method to be easily implemented, replicated, improved and upscaled for other platforms and libraries, unlocking insights that emerge only at scale, especially when combined with cross-comparisons and multi-year longitudinal tracking.

Figure 3: Overview of the data processing pipeline

FUNCTIONAL ROLES AND WORKFLOW DETAILS

PRIMARY SOURCES

After completing the Data Management Plan with CNRS DPO¹⁷, the OpenEdition and HAL connection logs were deposited on a secure virtual machine hosted at OpenEdition Lab¹⁸. Accessing and processing the logs is restricted to the CNRS research team and -- via a subcontracting agreement -- their data analysis service supplier, Ouestware¹⁹. Access control is managed by the SSH access policy.

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/11049557>

¹⁸ <https://lab.hypotheses.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.ouestware.com/>

THE RAW LOGS

Table 11: Overview of the platforms and their logs

PLATFORM	OPENEDITION		HAL (HYPER ARTICLES EN LIGNE)	
Creation	1999		2001	
Type	Publishing platform		Self-archiving repository	
Field	Humanities and social sciences		All	
Total resources (all years)	1M+		1M+	
Language of the resources	Mostly French		Mostly English	
Logging period	January 2023 → January 2024		September 2023 → September 2024	
# of events (access)	205,749,519 total	151,132,124 with DOI	231,455,659 total	228,399,632 with DOI
# documents (stock)	400,352 total	314,175 with DOI	3,816,686	1,327,967 with DOI

The connection logs²⁰ come as .txt files: one line corresponding to one log, i.e. one recorded attempt at logging onto the website. Those files can be hard to read for humans and cannot be directly computed because they are not in tabular format. They also contain a lot of traces left by bots crawling the platforms.

The Ezparse tools filters out robots, converts the text files into tabular data (.csv files) compatible with the COUNTER5 format, “a global standard for measuring and reporting content usage through normalised metrics”²¹.

Ezparse can be configured to enrich the raw logs with various methods²². It is part of a broader toolbox called Readmetrics²³, developed by CNRS national unit on scientific and technical resources INIST²⁴. This toolbox helps monitoring library resources. The Ezparse brick is fully Open Source, written in Node.js. It works with several middleware which can be forked and adapted by anyone²⁵.

OPENALEX DATA: WHAT IS BEING ACCESSED?

The first part of the information retrieved and added to the tabularized logs help answer the question: **what is being accessed? What is it about, and is it closed or open?** The supplementary data comes from OpenAlex²⁶, “a fully open catalogue of the global research system”.

²⁰ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Logging_\(computing\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Logging_(computing))

²¹ <https://www.countermetrics.org/code-of-practice/>

²² <https://ezparse-project.github.io/ezparse/essential/ec-attributes.html#typical-properties-of-an-access-event>

²³ <https://www.readmetrics.org/>

²⁴ <https://www.inist.fr/services/acceder/>

²⁵ <https://github.com/ezparse-project/ezparse-middleware>

²⁶ <https://docs.openalex.org/>

The exhaustive list of the fields retrieved²⁷, along with their description by OpenAlex, and, where applicable, the underlying methodology used by OpenAlex to generate the fields, is the following :

- **id**: OpenAlex identifier
- **type**: OpenAlex publication type
- **open_access**: OpenAlex Open Access mode²⁸
- **domains**: OpenAlex Topic level 1
- **fields**: OpenAlex Topic level 2
- **subfields**: OpenAlex Topic level 3²⁹
- **apc_list**: APC amount required by the publisher in US\$
- **apc_paid**: APC amount paid by the author in US\$
- **cited_by_count**: number of citations according to Open Alex
- **cited_by_api_url**: list of citations according to Open Alex
- **fwci**: Field-weighted Citation Impact³⁰
- **funders**: Research funders
- **sustainable_development_goals**: a predicted probability of the work's relevance for one or several of the 17 sustainable development goals³¹

IPINFO & NACE DATA: WHO IS ACCESSING?

The second part of the information retrieved helps answer the question: **who is accessing?** Each consultation event contains the IP address of the user who reached a specific website. An IP address “is a numerical label such as *192.0.2.1* that is assigned to a device connected to a computer network that uses the Internet Protocol for communication”³².

In some cases, organisations buy several consecutive static IP addresses: IP ranges. As organizations, they also buy domain names. Our IP data provider Ipinfo tells which domain names are linked to which IP ranges, and gives reliable information about the IP address, such as its geolocation and a basic sectorial classification (governmental, education, hosting, ISP, business).

The main challenge was to find a way to classify those IP ranges into sectors that were a bit more granular than the societal/economic/academic divide (which is a convenient typology mostly used as an immediately actionable tool for policymakers), while remaining scientifically robust and compatible with big data approaches (i.e. excluding manual sorting).

²⁷ See here for an example of response from OpenAlex’s “works” API entry point.

²⁸ <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/works/work-object#the-openaccess-object>

²⁹ “For a detailed description of the methods behind OpenAlex Topics, see our paper: “[OpenAlex: End-to-End Process for Topic Classification](#)”. The code and model are available at <https://github.com/ourresearch/openalex-topic-classification>”. See here : <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/topics>

³⁰ “*Field-weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) is a snowball metric that takes into account differences in publication type, field (or more specifically, subfield), and year of publication to help understand the citation impact of a particular publication*”. See here : <https://help.openalex.org/hc/en-us/articles/24735753007895-Field-Weighted-Citation-Impact-FWCI>

³¹ https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/works/work-object#sustainable_development_goals

³² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IP_address

We opted for the NACE typology (the *Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community*, an acronym stemming from the French *Nomenclature Statistique des Activités Economiques dans la Communauté Européenne*). The NACE is the industry standard classification system used in the European Union. It is the European implementation of the UN classification ISIC, revision 5³³.

It is used at the European level, has been revised several times by expert bodies, and it is based on solid, well-documented guidelines³⁴. The NACE typology is a descending hierarchical classification. It uses four hierarchical levels :

- Level 1: 22 sections identified by alphabetical letters A to V;
- Level 2: 88 divisions identified by two-digit numerical codes (01 to 99);
- Level 3: 272 groups identified by three-digit numerical codes (01.1 to 99.0);
- Level 4: 615 classes identified by four-digit numerical codes (01.11 to 99.00).

It is available in RDF format (Resource Description Framework) and each section, division, group and class come with a short description. This study adopts the Level 1 classification (22 sections), because it was evaluated sufficient for the purpose of the research, and since the level of precision required for finer-grained classification given that the level of precision required for finer-grained classification was deemed too complex for the scope of this study.

PREPROCESSING TOOLS

Retrieving the scientific field of a resource is done pretty straightforward based on the DOI of that resource. Adding the NACE category of a user based on their IP address is a bit more complex. In order to do that, we developed a custom prompt engineering method to automate this classification. We improved the prompt using some of the techniques suggested by Schulhoff, Sander et al³⁵, using the open-source large language model Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct³⁶ run by the Huma-num infrastructure and a custom Typescript script³⁷.

This protocol shows how we performed the task of automatize the NACE classification of the organisation owning a domain name. For example, if we know that IP xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx owns "electricity.biz" it most probably belongs to NACE section D ELECTRICITY, GAS, STEAM AND AIR CONDITIONING SUPPLY (en).

To automatize the classification process, a *truth table* is established based on human annotation of a random subset of 200 IP addresses and their associated domain names. Three annotators hand-classified them based on the domain name if explicit enough, or by visiting the corresponding webpage where additional information about the organisation could be retrieved.

³³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nace>

³⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nace/guidance>

³⁵ Schulhoff, Sander et al. (2025) 'The Prompt Report: A Systematic Survey of Prompt Engineering Techniques'. arXiv. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2406.06608>.

³⁶ <https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct>

³⁷ <https://gitlab.huma-num.fr/path-os/automated-nace-classifier>

The annotators agreed in 89% of the cases. Where all annotators agreed, the value for a given domain-IP couple was simply reported on the truth table, as well as the most chosen value when two out of three annotators agreed. Where all annotators disagreed, a manual adjudication was made to report the value that seemed the most relevant.

The truth table was then used to measure the accuracy of the prompt used for automatized classification. If a prompt matches the truth table for a given domain-IP couple, we give it a 1. If not, we give it a 0. The final average score determines the most efficient prompt.

The inter-annotator agreement rate reminds us that this typology, as any typology, is ambiguous and will necessarily imply undecidable, borderline cases. It is sufficient for the retained prompt to near the inter-annotator agreement rate for it to be considered efficient; we don't require a 100% success rate.

Figure 4 Optimizing the prompt by performing a preliminary manual inter-annotation

We added a scrapping of the domains with Cheerio³⁸ and “fed” the LLM with a set of keywords extracted from the raw scrapping result to add semantic information. For reasons that we are not fully be able to explain –Large Language Models (LLMs) present significant explainability challenges due to their “black-box” nature –³⁹, the LLM performed at its peak (82% accuracy rate) when following this precise script:

³⁸ <https://cheerio.js.org/docs/intro>

³⁹ Cardon, D., Cointet, J.-P. et Mazières, A. (2018). La revanche des neurones L’invention des machines inductives et la controverse de l’intelligence artificielle. Réseaux, 211(5), 173-220. <https://doi.org/10.3917/res.211.0173>.

```

const classifyEntry = async (element) => {
  let classified = {
    name: element.org_name,
    domain: element["org_domain"],
    ipinfo_type: element.org_type,
    ...(await extractKeywords(element["org_domain"])),
    NACE: undefined,
  };
  // A partir de cet objet en passant les keywords on essaie d'obtenir du LLM une classe NACE
  // correspondant au domaine qu'on stocke au format brut dans rawLLMresponse
  try {
    const prompt = `
- Task: Classify the company based on its description.
- Input: Company name, website, keywords list.
- Rules:
- Base your classification primarily on the company's core business activity
- When multiple sections seem applicable, choose the one most central to the company's
operations
${lodash
  .toPairs(naceSections)
  .map(([code, description]) => {
    return ` - if the company's core business is "${description}" answer the letter ${code}`;
  })
  .join("\n")}
- If no appropriate classification can be found, respond with "N/A"
- ONLY RETURN THE LETTER no explanations, no justifications, no text.
- Company description: ${element.org_name} ${element['org_domain']} ${
  classified.keywords
} `;
    const response = await fetch(process.env.HUMANUM_LLM_API, {
      method: "POST",
      headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json" },
      body: JSON.stringify({
        model: model,
        prompt,
        stream: false,
        options: { temperature: 0, num_predict: 1 },
      }),
    });
    if (!response.ok) {
      throw new Error(`unclassifiable - LLM error (${response.status})`);
    } else {
      const responseData = await response.json();
      classified.NACE = responseData.response;
    }
  } catch (error) {
    throw new Error(`Error processing ${element.name}: ${error}`);
  }
}

```

```
// on retourne l'objet classifié  
return classified;  
};
```

THE FINAL ENRICHED MICRODATA

The enriched CSV file is then indexed using a popular and powerful search engine called Elasticsearch⁴⁰ along with its visual interface Kibana⁴¹. Elasticsearch reorganises the information into a fast-lookup structure, like a super-efficient index in a book. Once indexed, searches and filters happen almost instantly, even with millions of rows, allowing for aggregation, general statistics production and instant data visualisation, the latter being very useful to iteratively test data exploration hypotheses.

As explained in D3.3 (p. 67 sq.), microdata are aggregated in three grouping variables which correspond to the three identified confounding factors:

- NACE category
- Country
- Scientific Domain

COMPUTING THE METRICS AND DISPLAYING THE DATA

THE OPEN ACCESS ADVANTAGE INDICATOR

Grouping variables can be combined with each other, e.g.: *all organizations in the Nace N category accessing computer science resources from Brazil*. For any possible combination, it is then possible to compute what we call the “Open Access advantage”.

In order to do that, we compute for HAL several indicators in order to compare the stock of resources to the access to those resources in closed vs. Open Access, for any given combination of metadata, as shown by the two graphs below.

⁴⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elasticsearch> & <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch>

⁴¹ <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kibana> & <https://www.elastic.co/kibana>

Figure 5 Definition of stock and access

Based on that distinction, we can compute following metrics:

Table 12: Overview of the computed metrics

METRIC NAME	EXPLANATION	NOTATION
closed_access	Number of clicks on closed access documents	AC
open_access	Number of clicks on Open Access documents (bronze, gold, etc.)	AO
closed_stock	Number of unique closed access documents	SC
open_stock	Number of unique Open Access documents	SO
closeness_ratio	Share of documents in closed stock	$SC / (SC + SO)$
openness_ratio	Share of documents in open stock	$SO / (SO + SC)$
openness_effect	Evaluates whether open documents are consulted more or less than their stock share	$SO / (SO + SC)$ $AO / (AO + AC)$

By doing so, we end up having three possible ideal-cases for any combination of sets:

Figure 6 Open access advantage indicators and three ideal-types

As stated before, our output will be twofold:

- A static output, a CSV file with a pre-computed Open Access advantage indicator for all combinations of grouping variables.
- A dynamic output, where grouping variables can be manually selected in order to compute the Open Access advantage indicator on the go.

For instance, the top 3 values of the static output are following:

Table 13: Top three combinations of location, sector, platform, and field with highest Open Access advantage

PLATFORM	FIELDS	ORG NACE	COUNTRY	VIEWED OPEN	VIEWED CLOSED	VIEWS TO OPEN	VIEWS TO CLOSE	ACCESS ADVANTAGE
ALL	Chemical Engineering	ALL	ALL	10013	10318	562847	126674	0,32
ALL	Chemistry	ALL	ALL	43608	42283	2037166	519787	0,29
ALL	Energy	ALL	ALL	10667	7752	793208	135703	0,27

DYNAMIC AND STATIC OUTPUT

There are two reasons why we decided to opt for a static and a dynamic output, computing reasons and epistemological reasons.

Computing reasons

Computing of the Open Access advantage indicator can only be done for combinations between sets of grouping variables where either *one* or *all elements* of each set is picked out. Pre-computing allows for further statistical treatments, such as a simple ranking by access advantage indicator or linear regression to control for confounding factors.

Combining either one, several, zero or all element for each of the set boils down to computing the cartesian product of the power sets of all three sets, which is impossible in the imparted time and resources. In this case, the Open Access advantage indicator can only be computed on the go, which requires a custom data exploration platform where the user can pick out exactly which element(s) from which set he wishes to combine and obtain the computed indicator.

This is made clearer by considering the figure below:

Figure 7 Cases of combinatorial explosion

Epistemological reason

In alignment with the “quali-quantitative” research approach⁴², we designed our case study as an exploratory as much as an explanatory endeavour.

Following Rieder and Röhle’s⁴³, we believe that a companion website can “document methodological choices, provide in-depth information on technical aspects and [...] source code. [It is] an ideal vehicle to present results more dynamically and interactively. Instead of providing the research results as a closed, finished product, Web-based interfaces [...] allow audiences to explore them both inductively and deductively, involving them in the process of knowledge production”.

Quali-quantitative methods, when they materialise in a data exploration web interface such as the one we developed for PathOS, allows the user to move back and forth between *situation*, ie. a specific, situated case observed in all its richness and complexity, and *aggregation*, ie. with a generalizing focus on “specific observables” and “regularities rather than exceptions”⁴⁴.

⁴² See here for an extended analysis. Venturini, T., Jacomy, M., Meunier, A., & Latour, B. (2017). An unexpected journey: A few lessons from sciences Po médialab’s experience. *Big Data & Society*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951717720949> (Original work published 2017)

⁴³ Rieder B, Röhle T (2012) Digital methods: Five challenges. In: Berry DM (ed.) *Understanding Digital Humanities*, Houndmills: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 67–84.

⁴⁴ (Venturini, T. et al, 2017)

This is why we designed a web application⁴⁵ that allows for combining the above mentioned variables, by picking either one, several or all elements from each grouping variable and computing the Open Access indicator for this combination of variables, as well as displaying the top accessed publications and the top accessing organizations.

Here is a screenshot for all domains + all fields + education sector + sociology and political science subfield on the platform HAL for 17 different countries (combination type 3):

Figure 8 All domains + all fields + education sector + sociology and political science subfield on the platform HAL for 17 different countries (combination type 3)

Here is a screenshot for chemical engineering + all Nace codes + both platforms + all countries (combination type 2, top 1 of pre-computed Open Access advantage value):

⁴⁵ <https://pathos.cis.cnrs.fr/>

Figure 9 Chemical engineering + all Nace codes + both platforms + all countries (combination type 2)

It is then possible to give a closer look at the top accessed articles and the top accessing organisations, which boils down to asking the question : if we look at the configuration where all types of actors from all countries accessing articles about chemical engineering on both platforms:

...who exactly are the most frequent “viewing organizations” who try to access these articles?

Figure 10 Viewing organizations

...and what are the top read articles exactly about?

Figure 11 Top read articles

SCIENTOMETRIC LANDSCAPES

Based on a previous research project, we added another functionality to help further explore

the “scientometric landscape” formed by the full corpus of articles accessed for any given combination of variables. We included a tool called Bibliograph⁴⁶, which works in three steps:

- It first uses bibliographic coupling or co-citation to build a base map. All references cited by the articles included in the corpus become nodes of the graph. The strength of the edge between two citations is proportionate to the number of times they are cited together by the same publication (ie. they are both mentioned in the bibliography of this publication).
- Using a force-directed algorithm, the references are positioned by spatially grouping references that are often co-cited and spatially moving away from each other references that are less or never cited together, thus forming disciplinary clusters.
- Once the base map has been built and spatialised, metadata related to every publication in the corpus is added (keywords, name of the publication’s review and/or book, author’s name and affiliation...) and are added as supplementary nodes to the map. However, these metadata placed as nodes are not connected with each other (as relating to the same publication), but they are connected to the references that are co-cited in the same bibliographies.
- A force-directed algorithm is used again, but the position of references is locked, so that the metadata have to move towards the references to which they have the strongest connection. It is thus possible to see, for any given corpus of publication, a “scientific landscape”, that is to say a clustered space of authors, institutions, reviews or keywords that are brought together because they strongly co-mention the same references through their related articles.

⁴⁶ A comprehensive explanation of how Bibliograph works is accessible here : <https://www.inshs.cnrs.fr/fr/cnrsinfo/bibliograph-un-outil-et-une-methode-pour-visualiser-les-paysages-scientometriques>

Figure 12: Bibliograph interface filters for generating scientometric landscapes

Filters

Use the sliders to choose how many nodes of each type should be included in your network based on the number of records in which they appears. It is strongly recommended NOT to include the references occurring in one record only.

Your data-set contains 2000 articles.

<p>Keep the 50 works with at least 283 citations</p> <p>0 2000</p>	<p>Keep the 878 references occurring in at least 2 records</p> <p>0 30629</p>
<p>Keep the 0 authors occurring in at least 9 records</p> <p>0 4189</p>	<p>Keep the 0 countries occurring in at least 1516 records</p> <p>0 83</p>
<p>Keep the 25 institutions occurring in at least 20 records</p> <p>0 1445</p>	<p>Keep the 25 fields occurring in at least 1 record</p> <p>0 25</p>
<p>Keep the 0 funders occurring in at least 16 records</p> <p>0 52</p>	<p>Keep the 0 keywords occurring in at least 33 records</p> <p>0 1285</p>
<p>Keep the 142 sub-fields occurring in at least 1 record</p> <p>0 142</p>	<p>Keep the 0 topics occurring in at least 147 records</p> <p>0 1290</p>
<p>Keep the 0 years occurring in at least 152 records</p> <p>0 32</p>	<p>Keep the 49 sources occurring in at least 19 records</p> <p>0 655</p>
<p>Keep the 6 "accessorgnaces" occurring in at least 317 records</p> <p>0 6</p>	<p>Keep the 0 "accessorgcountries" occurring in at least 1551 records</p> <p>0 16</p>

FILTER AND VISUALISE

Figure 13: Example of a scientometric landscape generated with Bibliograph

By helping to dynamically move between the pole of situation and the pole of aggregation, such a platform thus works as a *compass*, showing *explananda* rather than *explanantia*. It helps forming new research hypotheses and exploring specific configurations that would require further inquiry and other forms of methodological approaches such as ethnography of uses and sociology of reception, or on the contrary, deeper statistical analysis.

Those configurations can herewith be aggregative, for instance: “how is it that users from Iraq, all categories combined, are much more likely to try and read closed access science in spite of a majority of the stock of accessed resources being openly available?”. Or they can be situational, for instance: “how is it that on this very day, the users of this very country coming from this very NACE sector accessed this very article thousand times as much as the month before?”. This last question is in line with previous, above-mentioned, log analysis projects that focused on serendipity and developed a tool called the detector of unexpected readers⁴⁷.

⁴⁷ https://analytics.huma-num.fr/OpenEditionLab/umberto_oe/

3.6.3. Operational Observations & Lessons Learned

TECHNICAL OR METHODOLOGICAL CHALLENGES

Such as case study poses several technical and methodological challenges.

CNRS DPO

The Argos tool⁴⁸ used by the PathOS consortium includes more than fifty questions, and CNRS required the filling of an additional form in its dedicated tool Revcil⁴⁹, as well as a five-page “Data Service Provision Agreement” and a two-pages “Information note on data protection in scientific research” that had to be published on each platform whose logs were analyzed. We also had to review and sign a four-page academic research agreement with our IP information supplier.

The negotiation regarding privacy and GDPR compliance issues, ultimately resulting in the uploading of the data to the dedicated server, involved a growing number of interlocutors, exchanges, points of view, priorities, and unpredictable delays, as these interlocutors are usually fully engaged in their main projects. The CNRS team interacted with the directors of the platforms considered (3 people), their technical teams (6 people), other PathOS interlocutors (2-3 people), the CNRS DPO team (2 people), our data service suppliers (1 person), the managers of the virtual machine used for data analytics (3 people), the commercial team of our IP information supplier (1 person).

THE RANGE OF REQUIRED DIGITAL SKILLS.

As appears in the “high-level overview of tools and dataset used” diagram, this kind of approach requires advanced proficiency in data analysis tools such as Elasticsearch, and in the programming languages Javascript and its strongly-typed superset Typescript. This applies to data collection, processing and analysis, as well as to the phase of web development required to create the data exploration app – which also demands a good knowledge of the React library⁵⁰. Proficiency in DevOps⁵¹ practices is also required to manage the infrastructure and deploy code to both server- and client-side environments. Familiarity with local, open-source LLMs and prompting techniques is required; advanced prompting, fine-tuning, and embedding-based classification methods would help refine the accuracy and granularity of sectorial classification.

⁴⁸ <https://argos.openaire.eu/>

⁴⁹ <https://revcil.cnrs.fr/>

⁵⁰ <https://react.dev/>

⁵¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/DevOps>

COMBINING HETEROGENOUS METHODOLOGIES, THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL EXPECTATIONS.

A methodological challenge in this case study was to try and integrate several kind of scientific approaches.

First, the PathOS project is strongly based on a primarily econometric causalist approach, which relies on technical tools such as causality diagrams⁵², counterfactual reasoning and the advanced statistical methods required to implement it⁵³. As we note in an introductory note of the handbook, “in the social sciences, the notion of causality is fraught with debate and controversies. Social phenomena are so complex and multidimensional, that many social scientists have abandoned the project of identifying clear causality pathways and instead decided to focus on the thick description of collective interactions (especially in the tradition of qualitative research) or on the detection of strong and weak association between variables and metrics describing different social dimension (but always keeping in mind the mantra that ‘correlation is not causation’). It is key to note that acknowledging these difficulties does not mean pronouncing the impossibility of demonstrating that some societal trends and political decisions are beneficial to society and have tangible and measurable effects. It means, however, accepting that this type of demonstration will always be tentative, reliant on case studies and illustrations and impossible to disentangle with certainty all from all possible confounding factors”⁵⁴.

That brings us to our endeavour to propose a more exploratory, quali-quantitative method that opens up possible interpretations and analyses about the access, use and impact of Open Science platforms. As previously said, quali-quantitative methods start from the premise that the proliferation of massive digital traces is a good occasion to reframe the way social sciences perform and present their research, between situated and aggregated knowledge⁵⁵.

LIMITATIONS AND BIASES INHERENT TO THE DATA AND TOOLS.

If we stick to the data that we actually collected and enriched, it is worth noting that the logs we collected only give limited and partially reliable information about the individuals and groups using scientific resources. In the following section “insight for similar future efforts”, we will share mitigation strategies and exciting challenges in the future study of the impact of Open Science.

GRANULARITY OF THE INFORMATION INCLUDED IN THE LOGS

The IP address tells us very little about, to put it a bit naively, the “real-world” individuals behind the screens, and moreover, this address is not helpful in considering relevant socio-

⁵² https://handbook.pathos-project.eu/sections/0_causality/causal_intro/article/intro-causality.html

⁵³ <https://scienceetbiencommun.pressbooks.pub/pubpolevaluation/>

⁵⁴ Tommaso Venturini in Apartis, S., G. Catalano, G. Consiglio, R. Costas, E. Delugas, M. Dulong de Rosnay, I. Grypari, et al. 2024. “Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook.” Zenodo. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14538442>

⁵⁵ (Venturini, T. et al, 2017)

demographic variables such as gender, social background, education level, racialization, sexual orientation or income. Such variables are indispensable in order to constitute the so-called “users” as sociologically relevant *constructed individuals*. The (more than welcome) limitations due to GDPR in the logs we had access to (which do not include javascript captured heatmaps or cross-site tracking, for instance) also hinders our understanding of the contextual, cognitive and affective (not to say libidinal) user interaction with socio-technical apparatuses and their affordances⁵⁶, and of the user’s *reception* and use of the resources that they are accessing.

Also, it cannot be asserted that resources are substitutable according to their openness status. What’s more, the same IP address can be used by several people, especially in big organizations where several devices connect through a single internet gateway or router. Conversely, the same person can access online scientific resources through different IP addresses, unbeknownst to the researchers. For instance, the employee of a banking firm can read the same article using the internet gateway of his firm and his private ISP back home in his spare time.

On another level, the sectoral classification we used, based on IPinfo and then on the LLM-based NACE classification, only gave relevant output on a small sample of the total amount of consultation events, because our partner IP info processed a vast majority of consulting IP addresses and either:

- (1) Marked them as belonging to “Internet Service Providers” (the user is using an internet router to access the platform)
- (2) Marked them as belonging to “Hosting” (the user is using a VPN to access the platform)
- (3) Or, could not provide anything about the IP address.

In none of these cases could we run the LLM for further NACE sectoral classification. Users with an IP address associated with an ISP domain name such as verizon.com would have been for instance wrongfully mistaken for users working in an organisation of the K sector (Telecommunication, computer programming etc). Now, they’re not. They simply use their internet box, and their sectoral classification remains a mystery.

Here is the breakdown for both platforms.

⁵⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Affordance>

Figure 14 Breakdown in NACE classes + ISP + Hosting for access events on both platforms

Secondly, it's important to note that, in some cases, these accessed resources do not have an associated DOI. It turns out that the DOI is the key that we use to retrieve information about the accessed resources from OpenAlex API, especially concerning the topics/subfield/field/domain classification. Consequently, there is a proportion of consulting events that land on resources that we can know nothing about. Our ground question being *who* accesses *what*, we also need to exclude all consultation events for DOI-less documents, which gives this breakdown:

Figure 15 Breakdown in NACE classes + ISP + Hosting for access events to resources with a DOI on both platforms

We need to focus on a smaller subset of the data in order to answer the question of “who accesses what”. Namely: the breakdown in all the NACE sections which users who do not use a VPN or an ISP and who access resources with a DOI.

Figure 16 Breakdown in NACE classes without ISP nor Hosting for access events to resources with a DOI on both platforms

This applies to 12% of the clicks on resources from the HAL platform and 5.97% of the clicks on resources from the OpenEdition platform.

LIMITS OF TYPOLOGIES AND DATA SOURCES

As mentioned earlier, since this approach relies on typologies (such as the NACE typology, the IPinfo typology, and the OpenAlex Topics typology), it is also subject to the biases inherent in those typologies themselves and, more broadly, inherent to the very process of classification. We will now outline some, but not all, of the main limits and biases of each typology. They do not imply that using these typologies is without value, they are worth keeping in mind for future endeavours and in order not to overstretch the scope of findings.

- (1) **IPinfo.** WHOIS has traditionally been the free tool to obtain ownership information on IPs and domain names, but it is limited: data is often incomplete, inconsistent across registries, outdated, and lacks a unified API. IPinfo stood out among other Regional Internet Registries aggregators, because it granted the possibility of an academic research agreement, offering a free access to a unified and structured API interface. It thus made it a more effective solution for accurate, large-scale data processing. Our reliance on its data quality comes with the limitation that, as a private company, its sources and methods are not fully open to scientific audit.

(2) **OpenAlex Topics.** This classification, which is detailed here⁵⁷, has been established based on a method developed by CWTS⁵⁸, by :

- Clustering the citation network formed by all publications included in an OpenAlex database snapshot from November 2023 (71M+ publications with out- and on- going citations),
- Assigning a label and a description to the 4516 found clusters using the Updated GPT 3.5 Turbo LLM, and,
- Tagging each work with a topic, a subfield, a field and a domain, those last three categories being based on the ASJC (All Science Journal Classification) scheme⁵⁹

This method, which has the great advantage of allowing the automatic classification of massive datasets, including publications which do not have on- or outgoing citations yet, also has following limits:

- In order to cluster publications, it relies on the principle that citations, that is, explicit mentions to other formalized works, are the only principle of internal consistency by which publications relate to one another, overseeing more subtle and less formalizable principles of intellectual affinity or repulsion⁶⁰.
- The three upper levels of the descending hierarchical classification on which it relies (subfield, field, and domain) stem from Elsevier, a private, highly controversial for-profit publisher⁶¹. To our knowledge, neither Scopus or Elsevier have ever published any peer-reviewed articles or data papers scientifically arguing the principles and decisions on which this typology is based.
- As a techno-centered approach, it seems unaware of the historical evolution of scientific disciplinary classifications⁶² and of power issues inherent to classification, a matter that has been, for instance, pointed out 50 years ago by sociologist Bourdieu and many others before and after him⁶³:

“Classificatory *discretio*, like law, freezes a certain state of the power relations which it aims to fix forever by enunciating and codifying it. The classificatory system as a principle of logical and political division only exists and functions because it reproduces, in a transfigured form, in the symbolic logic of differential gaps, i.e., of discontinuity, the generally gradual and continuous differences which structure the established order, but it makes its own, that is, specifically symbolic, contribution to the maintenance of that order only because it has the specifically

⁵⁷ [OpenAlex: End-to-End Process for Topic Classification](#) & <https://github.com/ourresearch/openalex-topic-classification>.

⁵⁸ See here : <https://www.leidenmadtrics.nl/articles/an-open-approach-for-classifying-research-publications> and here : Waltman, L. and Eck, N.J. van (2012) ‘A new methodology for constructing a publication-level classification system of science’. arXiv. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1203.0532>

⁵⁹ https://service.elsevier.com/app/answers/detail/a_id/12007/supporthub/scopus/

⁶⁰ See for instance Meng, X., Varol, O. and Barabási, A.-L. (2024) ‘Hidden Citations Obscure True Impact in Science’. arXiv. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2310.16181>.

⁶¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elsevier#Criticism_of_academic_practices

⁶² Space of Disciplines and Interdisciplinary Practices. (2015). *Actes de la recherche en sciences sociales*, (No 210), <https://shs.cairn.info/journal-actes-de-la-recherche-en-sciences-sociales-2015-5?lang=en>

⁶³ Bowker, G.C. and Star, S.L. (1999) *Sorting Things Out: Classification and Its Consequences*. The MIT Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/6352.001.0001>.

symbolic power to make people see and believe which is given by the imposition of mental structures”⁶⁴

(3) NACE typology. Thanks to its solid, well-documented guidelines, the NACE typology can be subjected to argumentative dispute and discussion, which is cornerstone of transparency, reproducibility and scientific progress.

We can therefore point following limits and challenges inherent to this typology:

- We already said that the NACE classification is relevant for IP ranges that are associated with the domain name of a company which is not a mere ISP or VPN provider. But it is important to note that this only applies to big groups that can afford buying ranges of fix IP addresses and domain names. It thus lacks granularity. This means that less formally organized social groups and communities, which often are the less privileged ones — such as citizen science associations, NGOs, social justice movements, and various interest-based communities — will fly under the radar and not be properly classified.
- As such, the NACE classification has been criticised for : a) lacking granularity and definition for some sectors, b) missing out emerging sectors and not accurately reflecting the current economy due to its very slow cycle of update, c) not capturing hybrid and multi-sectoral actors, d) overseeing size, turnover, or economic weight, e) misclassifying, underrepresenting socially beneficial, non-monetizable organizations or aggregating them with purely commercial operators.

WORKAROUNDS AND ADAPTATIONS

This is how we worked around the four kind of technical and methodological challenges (complexity associated with the data management plan and compliance with GDPR formalities, range of required digital skills, combining heterogenous methodologies, theoretical and practical expectations, limitations and biases inherent to the data and tools).

CHALLENGE N°1 : GDPR COMPLIANCE ASSOCIATED WITH THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN.

Workaround: Restricting the scope of the analysis from 3 to 2 OS platform.

We tried to work with the Recherche Data Gouv logs as third case study, but encounters several hurdles which jeopardised the effort, as no team members were able to attend any of the three data sprints we organized. The involvement of platform teams is crucial for alignment and case study co-creation. After the third data sprint, we attempted to collect the logs anyway, but the system administrator at OpenEdition (administrating the virtual machine that we used for raw log data processing) could not create the required SSH credentials in time, which made the whole endeavour impossible.

⁶⁴ *Distinctions. A Social Critique of the Judgment of Taste. Conclusion.* 1984, translated by Richard Nice, published by Harvard University Press, 1984.

Moreover, we gradually realised that the volume of data we collected—453 million consultation events from HAL and OpenEdition alone—was already enormous. The methodology we had just developed to analyse these two platforms, which are similar in terms of age and their Open Science content (mostly publications, including books, journal articles and conferences proceedings), might not be suitable for Recherche Data Gouv, a much more recent and less structured platform that had only just begun to operate and host not publications but databases. Leaving aside the third platform also meant more time for unexpectedly high administrative and legal work.

CHALLENGE N°2: RANGE OF REQUIRED DIGITAL SKILLS

Workaround : Use of service providers and organisation of data sprints for more technical subtasks

We dedicated part of our budget and collected additional, external funding⁶⁵ to work with a French data analysis agency, Ouestware⁶⁶, to perform technical tasks such as indexing the data and setting up an Elasticsearch server on an SSH-secured virtual machine, or deploying the final dataset exploration website. The system administrators of OpenEdition and Huma-num also regularly helped us (at no cost) with deployment and system administration.

Through three one-day long “data sprints” defined as “intensive research and coding workshops where participants coming from different academic and non-academic background convene physically to work together on a set of data and research questions”⁶⁷, we involved researchers, research administrators and programmers from OpenEdition, HAL, INIST and the Open Science department of the ministry of higher education.

CHALLENGE N°3: COMBINING HETEROGENOUS METHODOLOGIES, THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL EXPECTATIONS.

Workaround: Carefully distinguishing between impact, use and access and focusing on the latter. Restricting to a simple causality narrative and putting forward data exploration.

We conceptualised platforms as the meeting point between demand and supply for science and situated our case study as a study of access. We decided to differentiate access from use and use from impact (see graph above at 1.1.1), by stating that studying access is a *necessary, indispensable but not sufficient condition* for studying impact. We posit that the mediation between access and impact is *usage*, a situational, socio-cognitive phenomenon that can only very partially be monitored at platform level using sole quantitative methods.

⁶⁵ Grants received from the CNRS Social Sciences Exceptional Funds (2024) and the National Plan for Open Science (2023).

⁶⁶ <https://www.ouestware.com/en/>

⁶⁷ Venturini, T., Munk, A. and Meunier, A. (2018) ‘Data-Sprinting: a Public Approach to Digital Research’, in C. Lury, R. Fensham, and A. Heller-Nicholas (eds) Routledge handbook of interdisciplinary research methods. Routledge (Routledge international handbooks). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315714523-24>

To include the causal approach, we selected a small number of confounding factors based on the material we had collected (sector, location, discipline). We decided to test the effect of openness on access. As stated in the introduction of the handbook of indicators, “the fundamental problem in causal inference is that we never have the answer to the “what-if” question”⁶⁸. There is no parallel world that we could compare with our world, in which the same closed access works are Open Access, and vice-versa, and act as a control cohort.

What we chose to do, however, is to compare, if, under similar conditions (same kind of publications, same kind of users – coming from same geographical area and same sectors) openly available publications tend to be accessed more than paywalled publications.

Given the modest statistical expertise available, we have made the dataset available as a CSV to enable further statistical analysis, while concentrating on our core competency—the dynamic data-exploration app, which works as a “compass” to spot specific situations and start asking research questions, formulating hypotheses and developing further methods:

- Why are the top two most accessed articles by far, on OpenEdition (almost 1M views and 250k views) an article about the crime of rape in the Maghreb from the Berber Revolution to the Arabs attacks, and a Spanish article about scatological themes in popular festive songs?
- Why are there more views to HAL that come from the US than views that come from France?
- Why do open publications on HAL receive much more views in the social sciences (openness effect = 19,5%) than in medicine (openness effect = 7,4%)?
- Why do users from the transportation sector in the US accessing articles through HAL mostly look for computer science and engineering publications? Why are they equally trying to reach close and Open Access publications? Why is the most accessed publication about non-deterministic polynomial time?

CHALLENGE N°4: LIMITATIONS AND BIASES INHERENT TO THE DATA AND TOOLS. (A) GRANULARITY OF THE INFORMATION INCLUDED IN THE LOGS. (B) OPENALEX TOPICS. (C) NACE TYPOLOGY.

Workaround: We worked with data of sufficiently large scale, have identified the biases and restrict our endeavours to detecting trends on low granularity aggregates (countries, NACE sections, fields) as a step for future more refined inquiries (see next section).

While being imprecise, IP addresses, the associated domains and the NACE tagging, and the OpenAlex classification can still be considered as good proxies for a first groundwork of qualifying the “what” and the “who”.

We are aware of the selection biases and have specified which precise subset of data can be deemed robust for analysis. We work at a low level of granularity, looking at very general sectors and entities, which is compatible with stakeholder approach. We are not developing a multi-

⁶⁸ Vincent Traag in Apartis, S., G. Catalano, G. Consiglio, R. Costas, E. Delugas, M. Dulong de Rosnay, I. Grypari, et al. 2024. “Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook.” Zenodo. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14538442>

parameter socio-demographic analysis of the conditions of reception, appropriation, and reuse—whether in the short or long term—of openly available scientific content. Our tool is a compass, allowing for a first scanning and cartography of potential situations where Open Access seems to have a strong effect, which would require further digging.

The geographical location, despite being low granular (country level), is a good proxy for some derivable socio-demographical indicators, such as GDP per capita, poverty rate, Gini coefficient, internet penetration or level of education. The classification of scientific domains developed by CWTS and OpenAlex remains very handy. Despite the limitations previously noted, citations continue to serve as a central mechanism through which scientific texts and/or scientists interrelate. What matters is not to assume that it is the only one. Similarly, its Scopus based disciplinary classification retains strong heuristic value, provided it is not treated as a static, ontological truth but rather as a situated and dynamic typology at a given moment in time.

INSIGHTS FOR SIMILAR FUTURE EFFORTS

We now outline potential methodological improvements for future Open Science impact research (a collaboration, taking the form of a transmission of all PathOS work to the Open Science team of the French Minister of Research will allow to further refine the approach and the tool). First, we suggest eight research directions for implementation; second, we propose theoretical and critical groundwork that should be fully integrated as an epistemological safeguard in future projects.

METHODOLOGICAL IMPROVEMENTS

BROADENING THE SCOPE OF COLLECTED LOGS.

1. Spawn over multiple years, over multiple platforms worldwide, containing final and intermediary Open Science artifacts (articles, input and output data, communications, teaching materials, reports, software etc).
2. Include resources from pirate platforms such as Sci-Hub (for instance the download log for 2017 has been deposited on Zenodo⁶⁹) and from institutional libraries which grant access to paywalled resources, allowing for insightful and meaningful comparison between (legal, official) Open Science, closed science, and black Open Access⁷⁰.
3. After collecting the user's consent, the logs could include more precise usage data such as heatmaps, cross-site tracking, or fingerprinting. It is important to note, however, that this is ethically disputable. A dedicated participatory research add-on for web browsers such as Horus⁷¹ could be developed.

DEVELOP GRAPH-BASED DATA EXPLORATION TECHNIQUES.

⁶⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/1158301>

⁷⁰ Elbakyan, A. (2024) 'From Black Open Access to Open Access of Color: Accepting the Diversity of Approaches towards Free Science'. Preprints. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202409.0197.v1>.

⁷¹ <https://iscpif.fr/horus/>

4. The *referrers* contained in the logs could be analysed in order to generate a network of all the websites pointing to the studied platform, and a web app for web exploration similar to the one we developed could be designed in order to allow serendipitous discoveries.
5. Similar to Altmetrics which focus on citation of publications on social media, systematic crawling of specific regions of the internet (like Wikipedia, or a set of websites from NGOs with consequent web traffic, or selected governmental websites) could help find out whether the publications available on one or several targeted Open Science platforms are effectively mentioned on those websites, what graph and what conclusions about their use and “penetration rate” can be drawn from it.

Figure 17 How crawling of citations of resources made openly available by a platform could complement log analysis

REFINING THE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF USERS.

6. A survey could be designed and administered to the users of the studied platforms, with the option of linking responses to their IP address. This would make it possible to combine survey data with log data and thereby.

7. Should user fingerprints be collected, additional socio-economic profiling data could be acquired through data broker services. Note that this solution is invasive and potentially expensive.
8. Another way could be to rely on the geolocation derived from their IP address. This information can then be linked to external databases — for example, to the World Inequality Database⁷² at the country level, or to the Filosofi dataset from Insee⁷³ at the regional level in France — in order to capture geographical inequalities.

ACHIEVE HIGHER PRECISION IN AUTOMATED NACE CLASSIFICATION OR ANY MORE SUITABLE TAXONOMY.

9. Expanding the manual annotation dataset size and annotator pool to improve ground truth reliability,
10. Deploying sophisticated LLM architectures beyond prompt engineering—including retrieval-augmented generation, model fine-tuning, and embedding-based approaches
11. Expanding classification depth from 22 sections to 88 divisions to capture sector nuances more effectively

PERFORMING MORE REFINED STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

12. Adequately control for confounding factors using techniques such as linear regression.
13. Apply optimization algorithms to manage combinatorial explosions that surpass computational limits, prioritizing relevant parameter subsets and targeted queries.

STANDARDIZING LOG ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES AND AIMING AT REAL-TIME IMPLEMENTATION.

14. As sketched above, the required legal, technical and managerial processes for collecting, storing, analysing the logs on a dedicated, secured server and the multi-stakeholder log exploration methods such as data sprints could be further specified and translated into a dedicated handbook, addressing common challenges and giving mitigation techniques to lift constraints.
15. The log analysis methods could be implemented in real-time or near-real time in order to design monitoring dashboards that could serve short-termed iterative feedback for platform improvement, Open Science policy refinement, and raising awareness about the necessity to have free and Open Access to knowledge.

BRIDGING STRICTLY QUANTITATIVE ACCESS METRICS WITH MORE QUALITATIVE, USAGE-FOCUSED ANALYSES.

16. Based on sole log data, long-term navigation sessions could be modeled thanks to Markov chains⁷⁴ or other methods based on sessionizing and navigation pattern analysis.
17. Study the cognitive interaction of the users with the platforms. For instance, in a study conducted on Gallica platform, researchers have implemented a method called “Subjective

⁷² <https://wid.world/>

⁷³ <https://www.insee.fr/fr/metadonnees/source/serie/s1172>

⁷⁴ See for instance Romain Deveaud, *Modalités d'accès au savoir ouvert sur les plateformes d'OpenEdition* and Mohsine Aabid's ongoing PhD project : Aabid, M. (2023) *Analyse intégrée des usages dans l'environnement numérique COMMONS en Sciences Humaines et Sociales*. These en préparation. Aix-Marseille. Available at: <https://theses.fr/s379902> (Accessed: 18 August 2025).

Evidence-Based Ethnography” by using glasses equipped with a camera to study the interaction between user and computer while they were using the online library Gallica⁷⁵.

COMPLEMENT USAGE-FOCUSED ANALYSES WITH ETHNOGRAPHICAL FIELDWORK.

Using the methods of ethnography to study contextual appropriation and reuse of scientific resources, not only as the direct interaction with digital interfaces, but as longer-term changes, be they “conceptual (e.g. changes to awareness, understanding or perspective), or attitudinal or cultural (e.g. behavioural changes) [or] knowledge, skills gain or the development of relationships between diverse stakeholders”⁷⁶

A NEED FOR A MORE INTERDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVE AND CRITICAL EPISTEMOLOGIES

When it comes to the conceptual framework of impact modelling, scientific rigor requires that this framework should itself be subjected to scrutiny rather than accepted as foundational assumption. In particular, it is important to make sure that one does not just uncritically import concepts from public policy documents.

Above all, it is essential to position these concepts, tools, and frameworks as *potential options within a much larger array of available approaches*. Having knowledge of this wider range of alternatives enables researchers to make scientifically informed decisions when choosing which theoretical perspectives and methodological approaches to employ. It is important, at least temporarily, to take a step back from notions that seem self-explanatory but maybe aren't⁷⁷.

The following is a non-exhaustive set of epistemological issues that should be addressed from a critical, genuinely interdisciplinary perspective, both as a preliminary step and as an iterative, ongoing process in any project assessing the impact of Open Science.

CAUSALITY FRAMEWORK.

To what extent can methodologies from the natural sciences—particularly causal reasoning and causal diagrams—adequately account for the epistemological complexity of social phenomena, such as the diffusion and reception of openly accessible scientific outputs? What kinds of reductions do they impose on social processes, and are such reductions necessary to

⁷⁵ Beaudouin, V. and Denis, J. (2014) Observer et évaluer les usages de Gallica. Réflexion épistémologique et stratégique. report. BnF ; Telecom ParisTech. Available at: <https://shs.hal.science/halshs-01078530> (Accessed: 18 August 2025).

⁷⁶ Cole, N.L. et al. (2024) ‘The societal impact of Open Science: a scoping review’, Royal Society Open Science, 11(6), p. 240286. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240286>

⁷⁷ “Those terms can be seen as a set of “common places, in the Aristotelian sense of *notions or theses with which one argues but about which one does not argue* [which] remain undiscussed [and] owe much of their power to convince to the fact that, circulating from academic conferences to bestselling books, from semi-scholarly journals to expert’s evaluations, from commission reports to magazine covers, they are present everywhere simultaneously, from Berlin to Tokyo and from Milan to Mexico, and are powerfully supported and relayed by those allegedly neutral channels that are international organizations (such as the OECD or the European Commission) and public policy think tanks (such as the Adam Smith Institute and the Saint-Simon Foundation” in Bourdieu, P., & Wacquant, L. (1999). On the Cunning of Imperialist Reason. *Theory, Culture & Society*, 16(1), 41-58. <https://doi.org.inshs.bib.cnrs.fr/10.1177/026327699016001003> (Original work published 1999)

inform more effective policymaking? Furthermore, is it possible to reconcile systemic, model-based approaches with more situational, exploratory, and serendipitous modes of inquiry?

IMPACT FRAMEWORK.

How does one justify talking about the *impact* of Open Science rather than simply its effects or consequences? Why choose one term over the other? What added value does it bring? What is the history of impact evaluation, and what assumptions underlie it? Why are positive effects referred to as ‘impact,’ while negative ones are often described as ‘unintended consequences’? Why is intentionality introduced only in the negative case, even though Merton’s theory of ‘unintended consequences’—which is likely the theoretical basis of this expression, though never explicitly cited—does not impose such a restriction?

REPRESENTATION OF SOCIAL STRATIFICATION.

Why choose to represent social stratification as a simplistic, triadic, and mutually exclusive divide (academic / economy / societal), seemingly overlooking a century of work done by social scientists in order to develop more complex representations of society—among them Max Weber (*Economy and Society*), Émile Durkheim (*The Division of Labour in Society*), Karl Marx (*Das Kapital*), and Pierre Bourdieu (*Distinction*), Norbert Elias (*The Civilizing Process*) to name only a few classics?

REPRESENTATION OF SOCIAL GROUPS AND ACTORS.

Is stakeholder theory the most relevant framework to model the diffusion, reception, and the material and symbolic consequences of opening science? How can we ensure that it also takes into account power asymmetries and structural inequalities, and does not flatten the plurality of worldviews and modes of appropriation through an uncritical quantitative lens? Can it be combined with other approaches, such as audience studies or the sociology and psychology of reception?

3.6.4. Reusability & Transferability

CAN THIS SETUP BE REUSED BY OTHERS?

Our setup could be reused by others, but it would require some adjustments. Direct access to the raw datasets would involve negotiations with the platforms as well as additional paperwork to ensure RGPD compliance. A new agreement should be negotiated and signed with the IP information provider. However, reproducing the methodology with alternative input datasets is entirely feasible, provided one has the necessary technical expertise, since all the source code has been made publicly available online ⁷⁸and since we have done our best to rely on international standards.

⁷⁸ <https://gitlab.huma-num.fr/path-os>

IN WHAT CONTEXTS (NATIONAL, INSTITUTIONAL, THEMATIC)?

Our method can be used by:

- **University libraries.** We have been contacted by service d'appui à la recherche des bibliothèques (library research support service) from Université Paris-Est (UPEC)⁷⁹ that expressed interest in our case study.
- **National Open Science monitoring initiatives.** We have planned working sessions with the team of the *Open Science Barometer*⁸⁰ from the Open Science department of the French Ministry of Higher Education for them to draw inspiration from our case study.
- **Open Science platforms,** for building finer monitoring and steering tools.

WHAT ARE THE REQUIREMENTS?

See HIGH-LEVEL OVERVIEW OF TOOLS AND DATASETS USED.

ARE THERE ANY PLANS FOR REUSE BEYOND PATHOS?

As of August 2025, there are advanced discussions on replication of our method by the French Open Science Barometer and by Université Paris-Est library services.

⁷⁹ Research Support Service of the Libraries of Université Paris-Est (UPEC)

⁸⁰ Baromètre de la science ouverte

4. The Role of PathOS Tools and Data in

Enabling Long-Term OS Evaluation

Long-term evaluation of Open Science involves building systems that can be updated, adapted, and interpreted over time, as OS practices evolve and as policy needs shift. PathOS provides a set of real-world implementations that demonstrate how tools and data can be designed, structured, and documented to support repeatable, scalable, and adaptable evaluation.

This deliverable presents a portfolio of operationalised examples, each grounded in a particular domain, objective, and data landscape. Together, they reveal:

- The types of tools that can be effective for different indicators and data sources
- The kinds of decisions and trade-offs involved in implementation
- How data must be structured, transformed, or approximated to support specific indicators
- The limits of generalisation, and the value of well-documented contextualisation

These examples serve as **building blocks**, illustrating how others might construct or adapt their own evaluation systems based on similar needs.

Anyone designing future OS monitoring can draw on PathOS by:

- Reviewing the indicators tested and seeing how they were implemented
- Reusing or adapting tools published in GitHub repositories
- Analysing the logic of how datasets were constructed, sourced, or cleaned
- Understanding the trade-offs made in these case studies to inform their own

This deliverable shows that long-term evaluation requires making choices visible, methods transparent, and results reproducible. That is what these data and tools enable.